

22NRM06 ADMIT

Deliverable D1

Report describing performance requirements both for ITs as well as for the measuring instruments connected to them, based on disturbances in AC and DC MV grids (system voltage < 36 kV) and on future measurement needs in the frequency range up to 150 kHz

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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1 Introduction

One of the main objectives of the 22NRM06 ADMIT is to define a) characteristics of grid disturbances, b) performance requirements of ITs, c) accuracy parameters and uncertainty limits of VTs and CTs used for power system applications up to 150 kHz, in distribution grids with rated voltage up to 36 kV and currents up to 2 kA. To evaluate the metrological performance of ITs up to 150 kHz, it is necessary to define voltage and current waveforms and levels and working conditions. Indeed, the metrological characterisation of ITs is carried out by applying primary excitations and comparing the measurement result obtained with the ITs under test with those retrieved with a reference system.

To properly test VTs and CTs under realistic operating conditions (especially those installed in medium-voltage networks where harmonic disturbances in the 9 kHz–150 kHz band are increasingly present) it is crucial to identify realistic grid disturbances up to 150 kHz, along with their characteristics, to be used in the IT testing. This can be done by analysing the present knowledge (literature, standards, previous projects, etc.) and then by performing numerical simulations of power systems and measurement campaigns in MV grids.

As ITs' performance assessment is as meaningful as the applied waveforms resemble those found during typical operation, it is possible to correctly assess performance requirements for VTs and CTs up to 150 kHz by identifying the future measurement needs for power system applications up to 150 kHz and by selecting the IT types (LPIT, inductive, DLPIT), suitable for the frequency range up to 150 kHz.

2 Analysis of literature and standards about power system applications up to 150 kHz

The phenomenon of high-frequency distortion (HFD) in the electric grids, at both low voltage (LV) and medium-voltage (MV) levels, is gaining increasing interest within the scientific and technical community due to its growing occurrence and the associated impact. These disturbances are mainly injected into the grid by new installed devices, essential for achieving decentralized generation based on renewable sources. In fact, these generation systems are connected to the grid through power converters, whose switching frequencies are significantly increasing, leading to a corresponding rise in the frequency of the injected disturbances. HFD represents a quite recent issue, but numerous scientific papers have been published in recent years on this topic. Furthermore, various international standards have also covered it, to provide guidance on instrumentation and related algorithms and indices for the measurement of these phenomena. When measuring HFD in MV grids, it is necessary to use instrument transformers (ITs) to scale voltages and currents to levels fitting with the input stages of power quality (PQ) instruments. In this respect, the recently released Edition 2 of the IEC 61869-1 standard extends the concept of the IT accuracy class up to 500 kHz; however, the IEC 61869 standard family provides guidelines on how to test ITs only at power frequency.

The phenomenon of high-frequency distortion (HFD, often called supra-harmonics) consists of disturbances having significant frequency contents beyond 9 kHz. HFD gained significant interest in recent decades due to its increasing presence in both low-voltage (LV) and medium-voltage (MV) grids [1]-[4]. In fact, many renewable energy sources, as well as new electronic loads, are connected to the main power grid through power converters, whose switching frequencies are significantly increasing, leading to a corresponding rise in the frequency of injected disturbances. In particular, the main sources of HFD include energy-saving equipment, power electronics technologies associated with renewable energy sources, electric vehicle chargers, power line communication associated with smart grids, LED lamps, and photovoltaic inverters. Due to the negative impact of HFD on power quality (PQ) and on the normal operation of the grid, including power loss, heating of grid elements, aging of dielectric materials, and interference with equipment and power line communication technology [5], several challenges arise across the various fields of electrical/electronic engineering on how to deal with them. These challenges include the accurate identification and measurement of HFD, assessing their impact on equipment, understanding the transfer impedance between LV and MV grids, considering partial discharge effects, modeling grid impedance, implementing new standards or updating existing ones, and developing effective methods to mitigate their impact on power networks [6]-[9]. In the literature, several papers are focused on the topic of HFD. These research studies are focused on measuring the level of emissions generated by different sources [9], [10] and their effects on LV and MV power system components [11], evaluation methods of HFD levels [12], [13], propagation through power network impedance [14], [15], and mitigation strategies [16]-[19]. As regards the specific area of HFD, accurate measurement methods and indices for their quantification have been included into in-force international standards such as

IEC 61000-4-7 [5] and IEC 61000-4-30 [20]. In addition, suitable measurement techniques have been proposed in the scientific literature to measure HFD [21], [22]. For instance, Digital CISPR [23], Light-QP [24], and matrix pencil methods [25] are some of the proposed methods that provide different approaches to measure HFD, which differ from each other in computational resources, accuracy, and immunity to noise [2], [26]. As regards the measurement chain for the monitoring of HFD in MV grids, it must always include transducers to properly scale down the voltage and current to levels fitting with the input stage of PQ analyzers or, more generally, acquisition systems. For MV grids, the widely used transducers are instrument transformers (ITs), such as voltage and current transformers (VTs and CTs). Consequently, it is evident that the ITs metrological performances at frequencies higher than 9 kHz strongly impact the overall accuracy associated with HFD measurements [24]. From the standardization point of view, the ITs are covered by the IEC 61869 standard family. The recently released IEC 61869-1 Edition 2 [27] extends the concept of accuracy classes, previously limited to the power frequency, over five different frequency ranges up to 500 kHz. However, the entire standard family lacks indications on test procedures, methods, and specifications of the reference systems used for characterizing the ITs at frequencies different from the fundamental frequency. In this respect, the European research project EMPIR 19NRM05 IT4PQ [28], [29], concluded in June 2023, focused on building up the entire metrological framework for the accuracy verification of ITs from power frequency up to 9 kHz [30]. As regards the frequency range 9–150 kHz, a new project has recently started: the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 ADMIT [31], [32]. The most significant activities that will be carried out within this project are definition of accuracy parameters and related procedures for the performance evaluation of ITs, definition of realistic waveforms, development of new reference systems for the generation of alternating current (AC, 50/60 Hz) or direct current (DC) voltages (up to 36 kV) and currents (up to 2 kA) with spectral components at reduced amplitudes up to 150 kHz, and development of reference MV voltage and current sensors up to 150 kHz. The first key activity to achieve these objectives is the collection of all available information regarding HFD occurring in electrical grids in the 9–150 kHz range and the behaviour of ITs in this range. Ω

The most significant HFD sources were revealed to be photovoltaic (PV) power parks and electric vehicles (EVs) [17] and their charging stations (EVCSs), which are more intimately interconnected in the MV and LV grids, rather than larger wind parks and other large power installations, usually connected farther away in the grid an closer to the high-voltage level, with some exceptions [18], [33], [34]. In [35], a voltage HFD at 16.1 kHz was observed, in addition to the main HFD peak in the spectrum at the frequency of 2.5 kHz. The occurrences of this HFD indicate that they were caused by PV power installations in the considered grid. In [36], a dominant emission at 10 kHz was found due to the switching frequency of the power converter. The paper underlined the time-varying emissions due to the variation in switching frequency of wind turbine converters at different operating modes during low power extraction, with switching frequencies ranging from 7 to 10 kHz. Therefore, 10 kHz can be considered an HFD frequency component due to wind turbine converters, which can impact the network and connected equipment. In [37], HFD components were observed in the range 2–50 kHz for both voltage and current. Here, the predominant frequencies were 12.5 kHz, 16.1 kHz, and 34.1 kHz, with amplitudes below 0.1% and 0.25% for voltage and current, respectively. In [38], a measurement campaign in a distribution network was performed. The paper showed that the components of HFDs were primarily concentrated below 50 kHz, with amplitudes generally below 0.3 V, particularly around 10 kHz and 12 kHz. Moreover, in the presence of high PV penetration, 10 kHz, 26 kHz, and 36 kHz frequency components were found predominant, compared with tones at other frequencies. Finally, a component with 0.15 V at 126 kHz was found. Probably, this is due to the presence of resonances in the system, as caused by grid-connected inverters and their filters. In [39], a long-term measurement was performed at several locations with small-scale PV installations. The results of the measurements showed that there were two dominating HFD frequencies at 16 kHz and 16.7 kHz. However, no additional information was provided regarding the amplitude of these HFD components. The study in [40] examined the intermodulation resulting from the interaction between PV systems and electric vehicle (EV) charger stations, demonstrating that it produced HFD at several frequencies with significant amplitudes. In particular, a dominant frequency was identified at 16 kHz, probably due to the switching frequency of the PV inverter circuit. Additionally, lower-amplitude emissions were observed at integer multiples of the switching frequency, especially at 32 kHz and 48 kHz. Furthermore, the primary emission of the EV charger station was detected below 25 kHz, but during the charging process, a component around 100 kHz emerged, likely attributed to the switching frequency of the EV. The intermodulation between the main emissions of PV and EV generated HFDs at various frequencies, including 16 kHz, 32 kHz, 52 kHz, 48 kHz, 64 kHz, 68 kHz, 80 kHz, 84 kHz, and 96 kHz. In [41], HFDs generated by Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) in a LV network were examined. The paper highlighted

that BEVs can produce a high level of HFDs, which can significantly impact PQ. In particular, the findings revealed that the HFD components with higher amplitudes for BEVs charging at 16 A were concentrated around 10 kHz, reaching magnitudes of up to 1080 mA. Harmonics of this component were observed at approximately 20 kHz and 40 kHz. Furthermore, for BEVs charging at 23 A, the dominant HFD components with higher amplitudes were found around 45 kHz, with magnitudes up to 200 mA, and their harmonics were noted at around 90 kHz. In [42], a measurement campaign conducted in LV grids detected the presence of HFDs within the context of residential PV inverter installations. Specifically, peaks were observed at approximately 16 kHz and 19.5 kHz. In [43], the transmission of HFD distortions through a transformer from the LV grid to the MV grid was studied. HFD currents were injected using an HFD-emitting device, which can create components in the frequency ranges 3.3–3.9 kHz, 6.8–7.8 kHz, and 10–11 kHz. The paper showed that HFD can propagate with various transfer ratios (i.e., a transfer ratio of 0.5 V/V means that 1 V becomes 0.5 V) for voltage or current and from LV to MV, or vice versa. In particular, from LV to MV, the current ratio was approximately 1 A/A, whereas the voltage ratio was between 0.01 V/V and 1.0 V/V and depended on the transformer ratio. The transfer ratio from MV to LV was, instead, between 0.5 V/V and 3.0 V/V, while no information was reported for the current transfer ratio. In [44], an advanced converter harmonic model was introduced to study harmonic resonance when an ultra-fast charging station was connected to the MV grid. This model was used for the impedance calculation up to 2.5 kHz. In [45], the propagation of HFD in a MV network was studied, focusing on the frequency range of 2–50 kHz. The analysis was based on the on-site measurements carried out in a 20 kV public network, which included a small MV wind plant and solar parks distributed over the whole network and connected to the MV grid via dedicated transformers. The results showed HFDs characterized by amplitudes of tens of millivolt and high variability during the day. In [19], [46], the impact of voltage HFDs on MV cables was evaluated. In [46], the accelerated aging of MV cable terminations due to HFDs was addressed in order to provide recommendations to evaluate the risk of cable terminations' failure under the presence of HFD in MV networks in the frequency range of 2–150 kHz. This paper suggested not to overcome the 24% of the rated voltage under 20 kHz and 9% of the rated voltage above 20 kHz. In [19], the effects of HFD on cable insulation were analysed. It was shown that cable insulation degradation progresses faster under power frequency voltage with superimposed HFDs. The test conducted in this paper consisted of superposing damped sine wave pulses with a natural frequency of 7.2 kHz and a repetition frequency of 800 Hz to the power frequency voltage. Moreover, the peak-to-peak voltage was set to 15% of the power frequency peak-to-peak voltage. These parameters were chosen according to a numerical simulation, which emulated a 1 MW PV power plant connected to the MV distribution grid. The HFD distribution in terms of amplitude and frequency was also evaluated, focusing on a wide range of victims in [24], providing a justification for limits in the supraharmonic range based on documented negative effects. Such negative effects range from the already mentioned impact on MV cables, and cable joints in particular, to aging of capacitors and dielectrics in general, as well as flicker as acoustic noise generated by interference to electrical appliances and EVs themselves, to interference to electrical equipment; in particular, in the presence of electronic circuits and communications, as in the case of power line communication (PLC) technology. Being the base for grid monitoring and automation, protection of PLC devices and communications from interference is a priority [47]. An important part of this wide group of electrical devices is represented by devices for protection (residual current devices) and metering (energy meters). As for protection, the real risk is desensitization of the protection relay, for which in the presence of HFD, the tripping threshold is increased, with relevant implications for electrical safety [48]. Metering is heavily influenced by HFD, as demonstrated in [49], where devices working on different principles but equally available on the market and complying with the same standard reacted quite differently. The problem is not only susceptibility of the electronic devices inside, but the different algorithms used to calculate the active and reactive power, as well as the interpretation of the active and reactive power terms (as demonstrated in [50], [51] for railway applications under various amounts and patterns of distortion for rolling stock in 16.7 Hz and 50 Hz systems).

Various measurement methods have been proposed for identifying and quantifying the occurrence of HFDs in power grids [2], [21]. More specifically, the international standards IEC 61000-4-7 [11], IEC 61000-4-30 [12], and CISPR 16-1 [16] provide methods for measuring HFDs. The proposed method for measuring frequency components above 9 kHz involves aggregating the energy of the signal under analysis into predetermined frequency ranges. Whereas for frequencies up to 9 kHz the commonly employed frequency bandwidth is 200 Hz, a bandwidth of 2 kHz is suggested for higher-frequency components. However, it is important to note that these methods offer reduced computational complexity but may sacrifice accuracy, particularly for high-amplitude components. However, additional methods based on different techniques have been developed and presented in the scientific literature. These methods provide different accuracy and resolution associated with

both amplitude and frequency of HFD [2], [21], [22], [42], [52]. The different accuracy and resolution of HFD measurement methods can be attributed to the following causes:

- The susceptibility to noise: some methods are less immune to noise and may lose accuracy in estimating high-amplitude HFDs.
- Computational complexity: some methods require more mathematical operations during processing, affecting their efficiency.
- Measurement equipment: the sampling rate, resolution, and accuracy class of measurement equipment can affect the accuracy of methods.
- Calibration process and data processing techniques can also contribute to the variation in accuracy and resolution.
- Transducers and sensors: all of the measurement methods are influenced by the accuracy and precision of the transducers and sensors.

More generally, the developed measurement methods can be categorized into two main groups: time-domain and frequency-domain measurement techniques. The time-domain methods involve analyzing the waveform using cross-correlation and matrix pencil to process the measured signal and estimate the HFD components. These measurement methods include Digital CISPR [13], Light-QP [16], Numerical-Heterodyne [53], [54], the matrix pencil method [22], and the sliding-window TLS-ESPRIT. The advantages of time-domain measurement methods include high time resolution and the ability to effectively reduce the influence of colored noise on the measurement [22], [52]. However, time-domain methods have limitations in terms of computational complexity and accuracy in estimating high-amplitude HFD components. The frequency-domain methods involve analyzing the spectral content of the waveform. These methods use the Fourier transformer (FT) in order to analyze the frequency component up to 150 kHz [2], [21], [55]. The advantage of these methods includes the ability to provide wide frequency-domain measurement and higher-frequency resolution. However, these methods are susceptible to noise and require a higher sampling rate to accurately detect the HFD components. The main issue across all methods concerns the amplitude resolution of measurement devices in the high-frequency range. Typically, the input stage of these devices is designed based on the amplitude of the fundamental component. Consequently, when an HFD with an amplitude below 5% of the fundamental component is present, the resolution of the measured components diminishes compared to the fundamental component. To address this issue, many measurement approaches include a high-pass filter to strongly attenuate the amplitude of the fundamental component. In this way, the input stage is designed to fit the high-frequency component, optimizing the amplitude resolution for HFDs. However, it is worth noting that scientific literature lacks papers addressing the metrological characterization of sensors, transducers, and high-pass filters specifically developed for MV applications from 20 kHz to 150 kHz.

The monitoring of HFD propagation in power grids through the grid impedance is a crucial issue since it can cause resonance phenomena. Resonance is common to DC and AC grids, as a consequence of the interaction between the grid impedance itself and the admittance contribution of connected loads, in particular renewables interfaced by means of actively controlled inverters. This is not only a characteristic of AC grids but also quite in DC grids [56] and can affect not only “grids” intended as distribution networks, but also specialized systems, such as electrified railways [57]. HFD from sources connected to the MV network, such as PV installation, wind farms, EV charger stations, and all renewable sources that use switching power converters, will spread through the MV network and, from there, through the transfer impedance to equipment connected to the LV grid. Furthermore, LV devices, such as LED lamps, can produce HFD and, from there, can be transferred to MV grids [58], [59]. Therefore, the equipment connected to both the LV and MV grids can be interfered with or damaged by the propagation of HFDs. Methods for grid impedance measurement are classified into active, passive, and quasi-passive methods, each with its own advantages and disadvantages [60]. Active methods are the most accurate, as they rely on a test signal injected into the grid. The shape of the test signal may vary, from ideally a pulse to a swept sine, or a combination of sinusoidal components at selected prime frequencies, or a pseudo-random binary sequence. The test signal must be efficiently coupled into the grid with problems of galvanic insulation and bandwidth of the amplifying and coupling device. Passive methods, instead, are based on passive listening of the electrical quantities and rely on transients and excitation signals that are intrinsic to the grid itself. Such excitation signals may be the spectral components of emissions of distorting loads, as well as transients due to maneuvers (load or compensator switching, breakers tripping, etc.). This

approach was successfully used to identify the railway line impedance following electric arcs, exploiting the high-frequency content of the arc transient and compensating the reduced number of samples with advanced spectral estimation techniques [61]. An impact evaluation based on the kind of interference between HFDs and power networks was introduced in [15], [18]. These papers considered adverse effects, such as audible noise, light flicker, tripping of residual current devices, and cable termination failure. HFD propagation generally depends on the impedance of the LV and MV grids and the connected devices. The sensitivity of HFD propagation to changes of the grid impedance at the delivery point has been modelled for the case of EV chargers connected to a LV DC distribution grid [14] and assessed in two experimental case studies [43], [44]. It has been found that HFDs can propagate through transformers, with different transfer ratios depending on the direction of propagation. Moreover, HFDs can interact with close devices in end-user installations, and the propagation toward the grid can either increase or decrease depending on the ratio between the device and grid impedance [62]. For these reasons, it is evident that a key issue in the HFD framework is the frequency dependent grid impedance measurement, which provides more accurate information about the connection capacity of points of common coupling, enabling more efficient grid utilization and optimization of large-scale generation plants. To measure grid impedance in the frequency range of 9–150 kHz, several methods have been proposed in the literature:

- A windowed Fourier transform is a commonly used method to improve the calculation precision and anti-interference ability of grid impedance detection [63].
- A three-stage interpolation-based measurement method, using cubic spline interpolation and Hanning-window-based interpolated discrete Fourier transform (IpDFT), can remove undesired components and deal with spectral leakage caused by FFT [64].
- Spectral excitation currents can be used to identify grid impedance, and different measurement systems have been successfully developed for different voltage levels [65].
- A time–frequency distribution method using a single rectangular pulse injection is employed for grid impedance estimation in the frequency range of HFD [66].
- Advanced methods for characterizing LV grid access impedance in the frequency range assigned to Narrow-band power-line communications (NB-PLC) have been developed and validated [59].

The main issue of grid impedance measurements is related to the emissions from several sources, such as non-linear loads or power electronics, and varies with frequency. These emissions can corrupt impedance measurements, leading to false resonances, phase distortion, and additional coupling of impedance elements. For these reasons, the identification of accurate techniques for the broad-band measurement of grid impedance, particularly at MV, is still an open issue.

Mitigation of HFD is a crucial task to avoid equipment malfunctions and decrease of the equipment lifespans and to maintain power grid stability. It is worth pointing out that both LV and MV grids are exposed to the same risks since HFD can be transmitted from MV to LV grids and vice versa through power transformers. To mitigate HFDs, several potential solutions have been proposed in the scientific literature. Some of these solutions are summarized below:

- Filters, such as EMC (electromagnetic compatibility) filters, can mitigate the HFDs by creating a low-impedance path for high-frequency signals, thus preventing their propagation into LV and MV grids [68].
- Resonance control strategies can mitigate the HFD propagation [3].
- Impedance control strategies can mitigate HFDs by managing the impedance of the grid and connected devices to counteract the propagation [62].

Commonly used techniques in the literature deploy filtering schemes, which can have different characteristics:

- Passive filters are widely used for harmonic filtering and offer several advantages, including energy saving and reductions in power demand [69].
- Active filters are effective in compensating for current and voltage harmonics, reactive power, and voltage imbalance in three-phase systems [70].

- Distributed multiple low-voltage filters can be deployed in random locations of a distribution system to mitigate harmonic distortions [71].
- Passive zero-sequence harmonic filters can trap two harmonics with one filter and are effective in mitigating zero-sequence harmonics [72].

However, all these solutions have several unsolved issues related to the behavior of HFD, especially in MV grids. The lack of recommended practices to assess the effects of HFD on the power grids makes the diagnosis and the mitigation of the related problems challenging tasks. Moreover, as mentioned in Section 2.3, HFDs can propagate through transformers and the transfer ratio and amplification of different components can vary, the propagation of HFDs less predictable. Finally, HFDs can cause interference with elements for power delivery and end-user equipment, which complicates discovering the point of injection of these disturbances.

A considerable number of international standards on the topic of power grid disturbances has been published. However, there is not a specific international standard covering the disturbances in the frequency range of 9 – 150 kHz in an MV grid. So far, standards have only partially addressed voltage and current components resulting from disturbances and signalling within the frequency range of 9 – 150 kHz.

The IEC 61000-4-7 [11] and IEC 61000-4-30 [12] standards provide methodologies for measuring voltage and current components up to 150 kHz. In addition to measurement methods, the IEC 61000-4-7 [11] and IEEE Std 1159 [73] also give a classification of power grid disturbances as conducted low-frequency and high-frequency phenomena. It is worth noting that the terms high frequency and low frequency in these standards are not defined in terms of a specific frequency threshold but instead indicate the relative difference in the frequency content of the phenomena listed in these categories. The main disturbances in the frequency range 9 – 150 kHz considered by the standards are the induced continuous wave (CW) voltage or currents, unidirectional transients, and oscillatory transients. However, the standards do not set specific limits to these disturbances for voltage and current in MV grids.

TABLE 1: RELEVANT INTERNATIONAL STANDARD FAMILIES DEALING WITH HFDs

Reviewed International Standards	
Voltage characteristics of electricity supplied by public distribution network	EN 50160 IEC 62749
Recommended practice for monitoring electric power quality	IEEE 1159
Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)	IEC 61000
Instrument transformers	IEC 61869 IEC 60044

As previously outlined, the measurement of HFD in MV grids requires the use of ITs. Consequently, the frequency behaviour of ITs significantly influences the accuracy associated with the measurement of these phenomena. In this respect, the IEC 61869-1 Ed.2 standard [74], which has been recently released, introduces new frequency accuracy class extensions for ITs up to 500 kHz. More specifically, it introduces five different extensions (WB0 to WB4) that differ in the covered frequency range. The WB0 class, which prescribes limits up to the 13th harmonic, is indicated as mandatory for Low Power Instrument Transformers (LPIT) and SAMUs (Stand Alone Merging Units), whereas the other extensions (WB1 to WB4) are optional. Regarding inductive IT, no wideband class extension is mandatory, not even the WB0.

However, the standard [74], but also the entire IEC 61869 standard family, does not provide guidelines on how to test ITs to verify their accuracy class at frequencies different from the power frequency (i.e. 50/60 Hz). Specifically, it does not specify the type of test signal to be used, i.e., whether the tests should be performed at reduced or nominal voltage. In this context, everything remains at the discretion of metrological institutes

and testing laboratories intending to verify the accuracy of ITs according to the classes limited provided by the standard.

The traceable characterization of ITs, with reference to AC and DC grids applications, at frequencies different from the fundamental, currently represents an open issue for National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and other metrological communities. Consequently, several European research projects have been funded in recent years to address this issue. This section aims to provide a concise review of previous research projects conducted over the years. For brevity, only key findings from these projects are presented here and detailed information can be accessed through referenced papers and webpages.

The EMRP ENG52 Smart Grid II [75], [76] was funded with the main aim of implementing a comprehensive metrology framework for Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs). Specifically, the project has focused on meeting the accurate calibration requirements for PMUs and their associated transducers, crucial for monitoring the stability of distribution networks. Additionally, the project has emphasized the need for innovative synchronized grid measurement techniques to analyse the propagation of PQ disturbances in networks, identify significant sources of disturbance and measure network impedance.

In the framework of the European project Smart Grid II, an optimised non-invasive CT was developed [77]. A non-invasive split-core CT with nanocrystalline core material was developed. Three different split-core CTs with primary currents of 100 A, 500 A and 1000 A were designed and built. An extensive characterisation was performed to quantify the CTs performance both in amplitude and frequency up to 5 kHz. The investigation of error frequency dependence revealed that employing nanocrystalline materials for CT core construction allows their utilization within a frequency range of up to 5 kHz, with ratio error variations on the order of a few hundred $\mu\text{A}/\text{A}$.

Within the Smart Grid II project, calibration facilities have been developed for the calibration of inductive MV VTs under distorted realistic voltages up to 30 kV and frequency content lower than 7 kHz [77]. Specifications and constraints of the facility for the frequency-dependent calibration of MV inductive VTs were identified, considering a range of voltages from 1 kV up to 30 kV with superimposed harmonics up to the 50th. Two possible generation and measurement setups were identified and developed. The key elements of both setups are a power amplifier (30 kV, 20 mA, DC to 30 kHz, with full generation capabilities up to 7 kHz), supplied by an arbitrary waveform generator, and a suitably built digital comparator with associated control and measurement software.

The first proposed setup extends the one used for the two-step procedure based on a high-voltage (HV) capacitance bridge, which is currently employed in NMI laboratories for the calibration of inductive VTs at power frequency [78]. A second setup, more oriented to the calibration of non-conventional VTs with LV output, was instead developed to calibrate VTs by comparison with a reference sensor. The reference sensor, designed and built for this particular purpose, is a resistive capacitive divider with suitable shields introduced to improve its frequency response and reduce proximity effects [79].

The first setup allows for calibrating VT up to 10 kHz with standard uncertainty within 200 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ and 300 μrad for ratio and phase errors, respectively. The second setup produces similar uncertainties in a narrower frequency range (DC to 8 kHz).

Ratio and phase errors up to the first resonance were measured on commercial VTs with primary voltages from 1 kV up to 50 kV. Measurements were performed carrying out a frequency sweep with the fundamental at the rated MV voltage (up to 30 kV) with a superimposed harmonic of amplitude from 20 % to 0.2 % of the fundamental component.

A technique was developed for compensating ratio and phase errors of MV VTs up to several tens of kHz [77], [80]. This involved metrological characterization of the VT over a wide frequency range, followed by cascading a device with a frequency response equal to the transducer inverse transfer function to compensate for systematic deviations. An impulse infinite response digital filter was adopted for this purpose, with its complex transfer function factorized in second-order sections. An objective function was defined to identify the best set of coefficients to fit the given transducer, using a hybrid scheme combining stochastic and deterministic approaches to minimize fitting errors. The technique was applied to compensate for the behaviour of a 50 kV VT, resulting in significant improvement in its frequency response up to 5 kHz. The MATLAB implementation of the filter showed substantial enhancement in frequency response, which was further implemented by using a PXI platform. Testing on a $55/\sqrt{3}$ kV VT demonstrated compliance with standard limits up to 4 kHz, with a

significant reduction in resonance peak after compensation. Lastly, the compensating filter for a 1 kV VT was successfully implemented [81], [82].

The project 18NRM05 SupraEMI [83], [84] dealt with the development of a metrological framework for the measurement of disturbances in the LV grids from 2 kHz to 150 kHz [85]. Within this project, a new measurement method for HFDs was proposed and tested in laboratory and onsite in different LV grids [86].

The new method was developed with the objective of updating the existing international standard IEC 61000-4-30 [12], which defines PQ measurement methods for power grids.

A major constraint on the development of the method was the need to demonstrate compatibility with a historic radio standard defined in CISPR 16-1-1 [13] which is used with an analogue radio receiver to sweep across the frequency band to look for emissions. This standard includes the 2-150 kHz band and as such has established itself in several EMC and PQ standards as the only available measurement method. For example, the basis of EMC is the definition of compatibility levels which is the maximum level of interference on the electricity grid for which any connected appliance should ever expect to be exposed to. The compatibility levels must be measured and monitored in grids, but in the absence of a suitable measurement method, the committee in charge used to refer to [13], thus creating the constraint that a new practical method for grid measurements must respect.

The method had to resolve the amplitude of emissions in the 2-150 kHz range which implies a decision on the frequency resolution for each component in the spectrum. The higher the resolution, the more data the instrument will be produced, leading to issues of storage, data presentation and interpretation. However, if the resolution is too low, it will not be possible to determine the emission problem frequencies preventing the tracing of the source of the emission and its mitigation. As a compromise, a frequency resolution of 200 Hz was chosen. Computationally, calculating the 2-150 kHz magnitude spectrum is extremely demanding and the algorithm used needs to be as efficient as possible. Therefore, the processing requirements of the instrument are realistic within the low-cost constraints, which over the 2-150 kHz spectrum leads to 740 frequency results every measurement period.

Defining the measurement period (and time resolution) has similar constraints on storage and interpretation and is also fundamentally constrained by the selection of the frequency resolution. A basic measurement update time of 200 ms (every ~10 cycles of a 50 Hz grid) was selected and aggregation over periods of 3 s and 10 minutes was suggested for compatibility level surveys to reduce storage and interpretation issues. The aggregation is obtained, for each frequency interval, by the square root of the square sum of the corresponding phasors evaluated from every 200 ms intervals involved in the aggregation period.

The required accuracy of the measurement (including method and instrumentation) is 10 % at each measured frequency for all magnitude values greater than 5 % of the instrument range.

Emissions usually cause problems for equipment connected to the grid, which are generally considered in terms of the peak value and the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the emission. So, the new method was conceived to be able to measure both peak and RMS of the individual frequency values across the spectrum. CISPR 16-1-1 already addresses these measurements but introduces a third type, called the quasi-peak value, which is based on an analogue circuit implementing a peak hold and decay function. IEC SC77A WG8 has chosen this quasi-peak value to be the basis of compatibility levels. Therefore, the new method had to produce this quasi-peak output too, using digital filters [87].

The main purpose of the EMPIR 16ENG04 MyRailS was the development of both laboratory and on-board train calibration and measurement setups and robust data processing algorithms to enable high accuracy energy and PQ measurements under highly dynamic electrical conditions. The envisaged frequencies ranged from a few hertz up to 5 kHz for AC systems and up to 3 kHz for DC systems. The uncertainty targets for laboratory calibrations were 0.5 % and 0.1 % for AC and DC systems, respectively, and 0.4 % for on-board calibration of DC systems.

In this context, within the MyRailS project a new system for the generation of high voltage waveforms up to 25 kV- 50 Hz and 15 kV-16.7 Hz with harmonics up to 5 kHz and phase-fired current waveforms going up to 500 A and harmonics up to 5 kHz was developed [88]. In particular, the developed AC calibration facility can generate:

- A sinusoidal high voltage up to 25 kV, 50 Hz or 15 kV 16.7 Hz with up to 5 kHz harmonic content.

- A sinusoidal current (50 Hz or 16.7 Hz) up to 500 A RMS value and up to 5 kHz harmonic content.

Moreover, in the framework of this project, a DC power measuring system was developed [89]. It was able to generate DC power (phantom power) up to 8 MW with the supply voltage ranging from 1 kV to 4 kV and current from 10 A to 2000 A and with a superimposed ripple with arbitrary frequency content up to 15 kHz for the voltage and 600 Hz for the current [90].

The EMPiR project Future Grid II [91] provided missing solutions for the calibration and the timing of the digital substation instrumentation according to IEC 61850 [92]. The main objectives of the Future Grid II project were:

1. Establish calibration methods to support testing of digital instrument transformers.
2. Provide references for instruments with digital input or output.
3. Develop tools for devices that exploit sampled values in digital substations.
4. Create traceable references for the verification of time and synchronization methods.

In the framework of this project, a “universal” comparator was developed and characterized, able to compare the output of any type of transducer (voltage or current, conventional or non-conventional, analogue or digital) in the presence of PQ or PMU (intending here the typical voltage or current phenomena used to evaluate the accuracy of a PMU [93]) events with a frequency spectrum up to 9 kHz [94]. The developed “universal” comparator also included synchronization with GPS or a different sync pulse. Regarding the uncertainties, 100 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ ($\mu\text{A}/\text{A}$) for the voltage (current) magnitude and 150 μrad for the phase were the target uncertainties up to 9 kHz [95], [96]. The universal comparator was included into the generation and measurement setup developed for the characterization of VT and Low Power VT (LPVT) with digital output in the presence of PQ phenomena up to 9 kHz.

Triggered by the needs expressed by the IEC TC 38, the primary goal of the EMPiR project 19NRM05 IT4PQ [23], [24] was to establish a metrological framework that ensures the traceability of PQ measurements conducted by various types of IT, ranging from calibrations at NMIs to characterizations performed in industrial laboratories. To reach this objective, four key technical goals were pursued:

- Developing reference measuring systems and methodologies to establish reference systems for ITs and assess their contribution to PQ indices' uncertainty.
- Establishing methods and procedures for calibrating ITs, including adherence to grid PQ disturbance limits outlined in current standards.
- Defining an "IT PQ Accuracy Class" for different types of ITs and PQ phenomena, based on identifying an overarching PQ performance index (PI) for ITs and its corresponding accuracy thresholds.
- Assessing IT behaviour under realistic conditions, such as the simultaneous presence of various influencing factors.

In the framework of this project, a number of PQ phenomena with spectral content up to 9 kHz were analysed, and the typical range of variation of each phenomenon was identified [97]. Suitable generation and measurement setups were implemented in order to test different types of ITs in the presence of PQ events. In particular, reference systems were developed to assess the errors introduced by CTs, VTs and combined ITs in PQ disturbance measurements. The general scheme of the developed setups includes a generation section, a reference sensor and a suitable acquisition system. Utilizing programmable waveform generators and step-up transformers or power amplifiers, the generation systems are capable of generating stationary waveforms as well as transient PQ disturbances such as dips, swells and oscillatory transients with a frequency content limited to 9 kHz. The applied waveforms are measured by characterized reference sensors, which may include MV resistive-capacitive dividers, VTs, CTs with associated conversion stages, and Low Power CTs (LPCTs). Investigative efforts explored the potential use of a current comparator as an alternative reference sensor, demonstrating its feasibility. Digital bridges are employed to record outputs from both the reference and characterized ITs, with quantities of interest being evaluated either in the time or frequency domain. Standard measurement uncertainties are maintained within a few tens of $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ and $\mu\text{A}/\text{A}$ (μrad), respectively, for voltage and current ratio (phase) errors at power frequency, with a slight increase to a few hundreds of $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ and $\mu\text{A}/\text{A}$ (μrad), respectively up to 9 kHz. As a main result, it was highlighted that the simultaneous presence of PQ phenomena impacts the performance of ITs, suggesting that to understand their actual metrological

characteristics, it is necessary to test ITs in the presence of waveforms containing multiple disturbances. For instance, it was observed that for inductive VTs, the ratio error at the harmonic frequencies increases by an order of magnitude if the test signal includes subharmonics in addition to harmonics.

The experimental setups were also used to investigate the impact of single and multiple influence quantities on ITs' performance in the measurement of PQ disturbances. Several tests were performed under various conditions, such as temperature variations, burdens, vibrations, proximity effects and adjacent phases. The primary finding revealed that burdens and temperature have the most significant impact on VTs, especially near the resonance frequencies. For LPITs, proximity effects and adjacent phases were found to be crucial. However, the way individual influencing factors interact, and influence IT performance largely depends on the specific type of IT and its construction.

3 Numerical simulations of realistic power systems

The purpose of this analysis is the evaluation of the characteristics of realistic power systems for what regards the propagation of supraharmmonic (SH) emissions and their expected intensity, that corresponds to the "characteristics of grid disturbances". With the term "realistic power system" it is meant an AC distribution network including both MV and LV levels with an extension and physical characteristics (e.g. electrical parameters) typical of a range of real systems. The "power system" will include cables for MV and LV levels, a MV/LV transformer and sources of SH emissions connected on each side; such "sources" correspond to a traditional 3-phase inverter architecture with configurable switching frequency and output filter, realistically selected of the LCL type (as commonly used to connect to distribution networks).

The modeling results will be compared to those available in the literature, as identified in the activity A1.1.1. Available published results cover mechanisms of emission, typical distortion levels in LV and MV distribution networks, and electrical behavior of the MV/LV transformer with respect to SH propagation.

The model is implemented in Simulink with a MATLAB script governing the simulations and parameter settings. Simulations will check both the behavior of the transformer taken alone and that of the whole network, evaluating the following phenomena: transfer between MV and LV levels, attenuation of SH signals while propagating along the network, and expected level of SH distortion.

The network is composed of one MV and one LV line interconnected by an MV/LV transformer and with a range of loads connected:

- power inverter as source of SH emissions,
- resistive load to change network damping,
- capacitive load to influence the resonant behavior of the MV and LV circuits.

In the following the most relevant blocks of the model are discussed. In general block parameters can be controlled from the Matlab script.

The transformer model is a standard circuit with mutual coupling and stray inductive terms at primary and secondary, as built in block of Simulink Simscape. Resistive terms can be included, but their behavior vs. frequency is hard to determine (to this aim the findings of A1.1.1 may be exploited) and to introduce in the model, as simulations are carried out in time domain; so an average value representative of the SH frequency interval will be introduced.

To prepare the input parameters for the auxiliary transformer in below table have been considered. The parameters selected are as follows:

Parameter or characteristic	Value
Nominal apparent power for primary (HV), S (kVA)	100
Percentage impedance between HV and LV %	4
No load losses (W)	1000
Full load losses (W)	5520
No load current (% of nominal current)	2

Primary voltage, V1 (kV)	11
Secondary voltage, V2 (kV)	0.4
Vector group	Dyn11
Nominal frequency (Hz)	50

The parameters of the equivalent circuit can be determined by open-circuit (no-load) and short-circuit (load) tests. The open-circuit test determines the shunt parameters of the simplified equivalent circuit of Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: SIMPLIFIED TRANSFORMER EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT

The leakage impedance value is much smaller than those of the shunt branch parameters. Therefore, the voltage drop in the resistance and leakage reactance is negligible as compared to the rated voltage. The input power measured by the wattmeter consists of the core loss and the primary winding ohmic-loss. If the no-load current is 2% of the full load current, the ohmic-loss in the primary winding resistance is just 0.04% of the load loss at the rated current; the value of the winding loss is negligible as compared to the core loss. Hence, the entire wattmeter reading can be taken as the core loss.

FIGURE 2: OPEN CIRCUIT TEST CIRCUIT

Using the below formulas, we derive the value from m-file.

$$P_c = V_{HV} * I_0 * \cos \theta$$

$$\cos \theta = \frac{P_c}{V_{HV} * I_0}$$

$$I_c = \frac{P_c}{V_{HV}^2}$$

$$I_{rhv} = \frac{S}{\sqrt{3} * V_{HV}}$$

$$I_0 = 0.01 * I_{rhv}$$

$$I_m = \sqrt{I_0^2 - I_c^2}$$

$$R_c = \frac{V_{HV}}{I_c}, X_m = \frac{V_{HV}}{I_m}, L_m = \frac{X_m}{2\pi f}$$

where:

- P_c is no load losses per phase (also referred as P_{nl}), X_m is magnetising reactance,
- R_c is core loss resistance,
- V_{HV} is HV side voltage per phase, I_c is current flowing in R_c branch, I_m is current flowing in X_m branch, I_o is no load current,
- I_{rhv} is rated current in HV winding.

A short-circuit test is done to measure the load loss and leakage impedance of the transformer. For a transformer having 4% leakage impedance, the voltage required to circulate the rated currents is 4% of the rated voltage, with one of the windings short-circuited. Since the core loss varies approximately in the square proportion of the applied voltage, with 5% voltage across R_c , it is just 0.25% of the core loss at the rated voltage. Hence, the entire loss measured by the wattmeter is almost equal to the load loss of the transformer.

FIGURE 3: SHORT CIRCUIT TEST CIRCUIT

The parameters of the equivalent circuit, $R_{eq} (= R_1 + R_2)$ and $X_{eq} (= X_{L1} + X_{L2})$, can now be determined from the measured quantities.

It is considered that $R_1 = R_2 = R_{eq}/2$ and $X_{L1} = X_{L2} = X_{eq}/2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \%R_{eq} &= \frac{P_{fl} * 100}{S} \\ \%X_{eq} &= \sqrt{\%Z_{eq}^2 - \%R_{eq}^2} \\ X_{eqHV} &= \frac{\%X_{eq}}{10} * Z_{bHV} \\ X_{eqLV1} &= \frac{\%X_{eq} * 9}{10 * a * a} * Z_{bHV} \\ X_{eqLV2} &= \frac{\%X_{eq} * 9}{10 * b * b} * Z_{bHV} \end{aligned}$$

where: R_{eq} is equivalent resistance of primary and secondary, X_{eq} is equivalent reactance of primary and secondary, Z_{eq} is equivalent impedance, R_{eqHV} is the resistance of primary winding (delta), R_{eqLV} is the resistance of secondary winding (star), X_{eqHV} is the reactance of primary winding (delta), X_{eqLV} is the reactance of secondary winding (star), c is the turn ratio.

To convert DC to AC, inverter has been added with PWM control. The switching frequency used is 10 kHz. Individual IGBTs are controlled, and the control strategy is based on dq control. Further details are provided in the following sections. The input for this converter is booster converter output. Thus, the dc link voltage 800 V is connected to it. The output of the inverter is fed to grid with LCL filter added in between to remove the harmonics and smoothen the output waveform. In order to measure the current, VI measurement is added in which only current is enabled.

The output current of the grid-connected inverter is obtained by the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) method, so it contains higher-order harmonics. Therefore, the L filter most commonly is used between inverter and the grid. However, the L filter suppresses existing harmonics and has slow system dynamic response large power applications. Besides, a high voltage drop occurs in L filter. Instead of the advanced L-filter, a high-order LCL filter has been used to correct the output currents of the Voltage Source converter (VSC). Compared to the L filter, the LCL filter is known to be more effective in reducing the switching harmonics, but has a resonance problem. Furthermore, the design process that determines the parameter values of the LCL filter is quite complex compared to the L filter. Due to various limitations such as filter size, current harmonics, the power absorbed in the filter capacitor, it is important to select the appropriate parameters.

Following steps are adopted in the design of LCL filter:

1. Selection of switching frequency ($F_{sw} = 10 \text{ kHz}$)
2. Selection of resonant frequency ($f_{res} = \frac{F_{sw}}{10} = 1 \text{ kHz}$)
3. Finding value of capacitance (C') $C' = \frac{0.05 \cdot S}{V^2 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot f} = 100 \mu\text{F}$, where grid frequency ($f = 50 \text{ Hz}$), grid voltage ($V = 230 \text{ V}$), power ($S = 100 \text{ kVA}$).
4. Finding value of inductance (L'); the LCL filter inductance chosen on each side of capacitance is 500 μH .

FIGURE 4: INVERTER

The grid with one MV/LV transformer, a branched line on the LV side and two variable loads at LV and MV sides respectively has been simulated using Simulink – Simscape. The topology is shown in Figure 5 with the detail of the equivalent circuit for the transformer.

The green elements are cable lines, modeled using a T equivalent with the cable capacitance in the middle. The dark red elements are resistive loads, with which the resultant damping effect was verified.

The grid is excited with a chirp signal at the far end (red generator) and the voltages at the point of injection (VLV or simply VLV), and at the LV sides (VLV2) and MV sides (VMV) of the transformer, are simulated. The chirp signal is made varying between 1 kHz and 150 kHz. From these quantities the frequency response is calculated by determining the instantaneous frequency, interval by interval, and plotting the ratio of the amplitude of the respective voltage components, obtaining two frequency responses.

FIGURE 5: SCHEME OF THE SIMPLIFIED SYSTEM FOR FREQUENCY RESPONSE DETERMINATION (COMPRISING A LOW VOLTAGE SIDE AND A MEDIUM VOLTAGE LEVEL).

The model of the transformer has been augmented by introducing stray capacitance terms, taken from [98] and transforming the capacitive terms for the equivalent circuit referred to the LV side (where relationships are well summarized in [99]).

The behaviors that were investigated are the influence of the long cable and its stray capacitance, the effect of the loading level (surely providing some damping), and the behavior of the MV/LV transformer with and without stray capacitance terms.

Simulations have been parameterized, as described in the following table, changing the length of the cable from 400 m to 4 km, its stray capacitance from 20 nF/km to 200 nF/km and loading from 10% to 30% of the transformer nominal power (having a fixed 10% load at the MV side).

	Green curves	Brown curves	Blue curves
	short cable (400 m) low cable cap (20 nF/km)	long cable (4000 m) low cable cap (20 nF/km)	long cable (4000 m) high cable cap (200 nF/km)
loading: MV 10% / LV 10%+cable no trafo parasitic cap FR1 freq resp.	Figure 6: dark curve	Figure 6: dark curve	Figure 6: dark curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable no trafo parasitic cap FR1 freq resp.	Figure 6: bright curve	Figure 6: bright curve	Figure 6: bright curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable no trafo parasitic cap FR2 freq resp.	Figure 7: bright curve	Figure 7: bright curve	Figure 7: bright curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable trafo parasitic cap 1-3 nF FR2 freq resp.	Figure 7: bright curve Figure 8: thin dashed curve	Figure 7: bright curve Figure 8: thin dashed curve	Figure 7: bright curve Figure 8: thin dashed curve
loading: MV 10% / LV 30%+cable trafo parasitic cap 10-15 nF FR2 freq resp.	Figure 7: bright curve Figure 8: thick dashed curve	Figure 7: bright curve Figure 8: thick dashed curve	Figure 7: bright curve Figure 8: thick dashed curve
loading: MV 10%+cable / LV 30%+cable trafo parasitic cap 10-15 nF FR2 freq resp.	Figure 8: black		

The curves for the three cases show a resonance that goes from the high frequency at the margin of the 150 kHz interval (green curve) down to about 25 kHz (blue curve). The peak amplitude is slightly higher at 25 kHz thanks to the lower losses. The orange-brown curves provide an intermediate resonance at 80 kHz, since the cable length is long, but a low parasitic capacitance is assumed.

Each case has a dark curve obtained for low loading (10%-10%) and a bright curve for higher loading (10%-30%), showing the expected damping of about a factor of 2 (proportional to the amount of loading).

It is observed that the increased loading has almost no effect at low frequency, becoming more relevant above 10 kHz.

This frequency response FR1 shows the effectiveness of a SH source far from the transformer to transfer to the high voltage side.

FIGURE 6: FRI TRANSFER FUNCTION (BETWEEN THE FAR SOURCE VOLTAGE AND THE MV-SIDE VOLTAGE)

Independent on the distance of the SH source, the frequency response FR2 provides, instead, indication of how effectively SH signals transfer from the LV to the HV side through the transformer.

In Figure 7 the three bright curves in reality are overlapped to the dark ones, as measuring directly at the transformer LV side the effect of the loading at some distance away is not relevant.

The low-frequency behavior of the previous figure is confirmed with a significant amplification instead above about 100 kHz, as there is no attenuation along the cable lines, but the resonant effects remain, with the contribution of the transformer.

FIGURE 7: FR2 TRANSFER FUNCTION (BETWEEN THE LV-SIDE VOLTAGE AND THE MV-SIDE VOLTAGE)

The results of Figure 8 have been obtained introducing the transformer stray capacitance terms: the 1-2 capacitance term across the LV and HV side is responsible mainly for the almost flat transfer curve, especially for the case with the largest capacitance value (thick dashed). The resonant dip is quite narrow as iron and copper losses at high frequency within the transformer are not modeled (they should include skin and proximity effect and core losses), but this is not so relevant as such short frequency interval may be neglected. What is relevant is that the thick dashed curves agree on a flat frequency response at a value slightly larger than 0.01.

Quite interesting is the effect of including cables on the MV side in some way putting the MV transformer terminals in a higher impedance condition: the black thick curve provides an estimate of the amount of disturbance transmitted across the transformer, with an efficiency of about 0.02 (so doubled with respect to the thick dashed curves).

FIGURE 8: FR2 TRANSFER FUNCTION INTRODUCING PARASITIC CAPACITANCE: SMALL CAPACITANCE (THIN DASHED) AND LARGE CAPACITANCE (THICK DASHED); THE BRIGHT CURVES ARE THOSE OF THE CASE WITHOUT PARASITIC CAPACITANCE TERMS

The results discussed so far indicate attenuation between 0.1 and 0.01 for the modeled transformer, with peaks towards unity at resonances. The real disturbance at the HV voltage level (in this case a Medium Voltage value of 11 kV with a turns ratio of 27.5) is obtained by multiplying the obtained values for the turns ratio, indicating:

- transmission values between 0.3 and 0.01 for SH sources far away and decoupled by the connecting cable, with an overall linear behavior with frequency provided by the inductive parts in the absence of parasitic capacitance terms for the transformer;
- transmission values approaching 0.01-0.02 to multiply by the turns ratio, resulting in an effectiveness of 0.3-0.5 for a wide range of frequency, thanks to the parasitic capacitance terms;
- the same parasitic terms introduce a significant amplification about approximately 50 kHz, for which an effectiveness of transfer of SH distortion of several units may be reached, up to an ideal maximum of about 30; in reality the turns ratio is bound to decrease with frequency for the reduced permeability of the core, so that amplification of some units may be expected as a maximum at such high-frequency resonances;
- it is observed that the switching transients of power converters have large dv/dt values able to significantly excite such resonances and propagate to the HV side.

A simple case has been simulated where the source of SH emissions is a PWM inverter, simulating the situation of a PV inverter connected on the LV side of a MV-LV grid.

The inverter is assumed 100 kW providing power sourced from a PV installation at 800 Vdc.

It is connected to the rest of the LV network with a cable of nominal length 1 km (tested to 3 km in one simulation).

The LV grid has also a passive load of 100 kW, configured with a 10% of inductive reactive power. The MV grid is supplied from a source with a nominal power of 10 MVA and the nominal voltage is 22 kV (the reason for selecting this voltage level is the availability of accurate data for the MV/LV transformer).

The MV/LV transformer is a 350 kVA transformer, with 4% short-circuit reactance. Additional transformer capacitance has been simulated in line with [98], ranging between 3 and 20 nF during simulations.

The MV grid is distributed over a length of 10 km (4 cable sections by 2.5 km each, for which cable capacitance was included with a conservative value of 100 nF/km). It will be observed that long cables provide decoupling of disturbance but can trigger network resonances at lower frequency and thus more critical.

The analysis was carried out to get the feeling of the relevance of the various parameters and an estimate of the intensity of the distortion caused on the LV and MV sides. As we will see, the combinations of parameters are many and various phenomena intermingle: resonances at LV and MV side, voltage drop caused by cable length, resonance and bypass of the transformer due to capacitance, damping provided by passive loads.

The inverter filter has been designed as LCL, as customary nowadays to interface such PV inverters, and similar power converters. The inductance has been calculated trying to keep the voltage drop acceptable, also in a control perspective, as longitudinal filter inductance causes always delay in the control response. A value of 340 μ H has been estimated, that selecting a resonance frequency slightly below 2 kHz, leads to a filter capacitance of 40 μ F.

The overall scheme of the simulated MV and LV network is shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9: BLOCK DIAGRAM OF THE SIMULINK MODEL

The results of the various simulations are reported in the following and discussed at the end.

Some simulations have checked the effect of the MV/LV transformer capacitance, decreasing and increasing the assumed 10 nF to 3 nF and 20 nF, that are two values in line with the extreme values indicated in [98].

The effect also of the length of the LV cable is considered, as it adds in series to the output inductance L2 of the inverter filter; it is clear that one of the purposes of L2 is right hiding variability of the connection, allowing stability and robustness of sizing and control. It is thus not expected a significant influence from non-dramatic increase of LV cable length.

The effect of the cables has been checked by reducing the length of the MV cables from a total 10 km to 4 km.

The effect then of the damping caused by the connected loads is checked by increasing the MV side loading from 100 kW to 500 kW and then 1500 kW.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 10: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED). NOMINAL CASE.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 11: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED).
TRANSFORMER CAPACITANCE 3 nF

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 12: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED).
TRANSFORMER CAPACITANCE 20 nF.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 13: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED). MV CABLE LENGTH 4 KM.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 14: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED). LV CABLE LENGTH 3 KM.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 15: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED). MV SIDE LOADING 500 kW

FIGURE 16: (A) VOLTAGE AND (B) CURRENT SPECTRA AT LV SIDE (BLUE) AND MV SIDE (RED). MV SIDE LOADING 1500 kW

Some conclusions may be based on the previous results, regarding both the effects of single parameters and scenarios (e.g. cable length, loading level, stray capacitance, etc.) and the general values that we may assign to this type of distortion, in order to establish reference levels for the instrumentation necessary to their measurement. The nominal case shows the following distortion level:

Starting for the nominal case with 10 nF of transformer stray capacitance between the primary and secondary windings, the effect is prevalently the increase of the resonance phenomenon, lowered to 50 kHz (from the previous nearly 60 kHz), with an increase of the MV voltage to 0.5 V with 20 nF.

	V_LV (mV)	V_MV (mV)	I_LV (mA)	I_MV (mA)
few kHz	10-100	10-100	10-30	<1
switching freq. (10 kHz)	400	400	3	10
first harm. of the switching freq. (20-50 kHz)	10-100	20-40	1-200	0.05-0.5
possible resonance	--	60 @ 60 kHz	--	0.1 @ 60 kHz

The effect then of the MV cable shortening is important for the current on the MV side, as shorter cables have lower impedance while pushing resonances to higher frequency. The effect is a MV voltage of 150-160 mV at 90 kHz, and a corresponding current of 40 mA. There is also a slight increase of the LV side voltage to about 20-50 mV at 90 kHz (at resonance). Increasing the length of the LV cable does not cause a significant change except a marginal increase of V_MV at the resonance of 90 kHz, from about 150-160 mV to 200 mV. The damping effect of the loading level is perceivable in the lower part of the frequency interval, where at already the switching frequency of 10 kHz it is marginal. The reason is that the loads are modeled as RL passive circuits, neglecting their capacitance.

To conclude, the estimate distortion levels should not be taken as maximum values, because there may be critical situations where local resonances may enhance voltage or current components, and because the nominal power of the involved elements is not dramatically large, although being on the high side. The estimated spectra indicate plausible values showing the range of variation of the main components, supporting consequently the definition of suitable likely minimum values that in turn define sensitivity levels for the involved instrumentation.

On the other hand, we need to underline that such low values would be of no interest in terms of disturbance or stress to components and, consequently, do not represent a requirement for the instrumentation.

4 Measurement campaign in a Medium Voltage grid

The purpose of the A1.1.3 measurement campaign is to assess and record electrical parameters in a Medium-Voltage (MV) grid. The focus is on evaluating the characteristics of current and voltage waveforms from 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

The campaign is performed thanks to Unareti S.p.a, an unfunded partner of the ADMIT Project, in "Ricevitrice Nord UNARETI" in Milan (Italy). The measurement campaign is performed by monitoring the MV voltage and current level of the MV/LV (low voltage) transformation cabin, designed for max load 1 MVA, of the electric vehicle hubs (EVHs) of UNARETI S.p.a, as shown in Figure 17. Figure 18 shows the MV/LV transformation cabin and the two MV/LV power transformers. The first one is a 630 kVA transformer with rated medium voltage (current) 23 kV (15 A) and rated low voltage (current) 400 V (909 A), the second one is a 400 kVA transformer with rated medium voltage (current) 23 kV (10.04 A) and rated low voltage (current) 400 V (577.4 A). In collaboration with UNIBO and SUN, a MV High Bandwidth Smart Termination is chosen and installed to perform MV measurements, as shown in Figure 19.

The schematic diagram of the measurement setup is shown in Figure 20. An acquisition system National Instrument USB-6366 with 2MS/s/ch, 8 differential analogue input channels and 16 bits is connected to Intel NUC MiniPC with LabVIEW System. The software acquires the data from USB-6366 using DAQmx driver and store the data in a FLAC (Free LossLess Audio Codec) file format with compression ratio up to 70 %, to drastically decrease the memory stored.

The MV sensor has Accuracy Class 0.5 with rated primary voltage equal to $20/\sqrt{3}$ kV and rated secondary voltage equal to 1 V. Moreover, there are two Rogowski Coils for low voltage side current measurement as shown in Figure 20, with 1/100 kA/mV and 1/333 kA/mV rated transformation ratio and accuracy class equal to 0.5. The measurements are performed during several months, and 80 GB/week of measurement data are recorded.

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Accuracy is crucial, as frequency-domain methods often offer higher accuracy for HFD detection but may require extensive computational resources. Noise immunity is another consideration; time-domain methods like the matrix pencil method are less susceptible to noise but can struggle with high-amplitude components. Computational complexity is an important consideration, with lightweight methods like Light-QP optimized for real-time grid monitoring and lower resource environments. Equipment limitations also influence the choice of algorithm, as the sampling rate, resolution, and input range of measurement devices play a significant role.

FIGURE 17: MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN LOCATION IN UNARETI S.P.A, “RICEVITRICE NORD UNARETI” VIA PONTE NUOVO 100 MILAN (ITALY)

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 18: MV/LV TRANSFORMATION CABIN FOR EVHS IN UNARETI. A) TRANSFORMATION CABIN PROSPECTIVE; B) 630 kVA MV/LV POWER TRANSFORMER; C) 400 kVA MV/LV POWER TRANSFORMER

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 19: DETAILS ABOUT MEDIUM VOLTAGE HIGH BANDWIDTH SMART TERMINATION INSTALLED IN MV/LV TRANSFORMATION CABIN

According to activity "A1.1.1-Analysis of literature and standards about power system applications up to 150 kHz", IEC 61000-4-7 and IEC 61000-4-30 there are several measurement algorithms used for identifying and quantifying high-frequency distortions (HFDs) in power grids. These algorithms are categorized into time-domain and frequency-domain approaches, along with hybrid and advanced methods.

FIGURE 20: BASIC BLOCK DIAGRAM OF MEASUREMENT SETUP

About time-domain algorithms, Digital CISPR is a digital implementation of the CISPR quasi-peak measurement. It measures emissions in the time domain, focusing on detecting peaks and assessing compliance with EMC standards. This algorithm is well-suited for compliance testing. Light-QP is a lightweight quasi-peak algorithm optimized for computational efficiency. It is designed for environments with limited computational resources, ensuring compliance with EMC standards. This method is computationally efficient and accurate for practical applications. The Matrix Pencil Method is a signal processing algorithm for identifying spectral components, particularly damped sinusoidal signals. It extracts frequency information with high resolution and offers high accuracy but is computationally intensive. The Numerical Heterodyne Method shifts signal frequencies to lower values to facilitate easier processing. It enhances time resolution and reduces colored noise, making it effective for transient and low-amplitude HFDs. Sliding-Window TLS-ESPRIT uses a sliding window and matrix decomposition for efficient frequency estimation. It provides high-resolution detection of low-amplitude components and is accurate for time-varying HFD emissions.

About frequency-domain algorithms, Fourier Transform (FT) is a widely used method for analyzing the frequency content of signals. It detects frequency components, offering wide frequency coverage and practical analysis for stationary HFDs. However, it requires high sampling rates for precise results. Interpolated Discrete Fourier Transform (IpDFT) is an advanced Fourier transform technique that reduces spectral leakage. Combining Hanning windows and cubic spline interpolation improves frequency resolution and accuracy. The Windowed Fourier Transform combines time and frequency analysis for enhanced precision. Localizing signals in time improves the detection of frequency components, making it useful for transient and dynamic HFD analysis. Wavelet Transform provides time-frequency localization of signals. It detects transient HFDs and varying emissions, such as those from PV inverters and wind turbines. This method is suitable for analyzing time-varying emissions. Spectral Excitation Currents analyze grid responses using the known spectral characteristics of excitation signals. This approach identifies HFD propagation and interactions within the grid and effectively analyzes grid impedance.

An FFT analysis was chosen for this activity to reduce the time of elaboration and provide measurement results according to international standards.

Moreover, the analysis index is chosen according to equation below.

$$Y_g = \sqrt{\sum_{f_a}^{f_b} Y_h^2} \quad (1)$$

where, $|f_b - f_a| = 10 \text{ kHz}$ is the range of frequency analysed and Y_h is the amplitude RMS of electrical quantities measured. For clarity, assume the first group starts from 50 Hz to 10 kHz, excluding the fundamental tone. Then, the second group ranges from 10 kHz to 20 kHz, the third ranges from 20 kHz to 30 kHz, and so on.

The measurements are performed over several months; only extracted waveforms are shown in the following paragraph. In Figure 21, the waveform of measured data for voltage current of Rogowski coil 1 and current of Rogowski coil 2 are shown.

The corresponding Fast Fourier Transform of waveform are shown in Figure 22.

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 21: WAVEFORM OF MEASUREMENT DATA OF VOLTAGE (A) CURRENT ROGOWSKI COIL 1 (B) AND CURRENT ROGOWSKI COIL 2 (C)

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 22: FAST FOURIER TRANSFORM OF VOLTAGE (A) CURRENT ROGOWSKI COIL 1 (B) AND CURRENT ROGOWSKI COIL 2 (C)

Moreover, the analysis is performed over all acquired data by following steps:

- Extract data from FLAC file
- Perform FFT
- Extract Y_g for each band group up to 180 kHz and collect them in a matrix

- Extract mean, max, and min values for each band group.

Figure 23 shows these values performed over all acquisition time. The maximum value of Y_g (red dashed line) starts at a very high value for band group Y_1 and significantly decreases as we progress toward later band groups up to 150 kHz. After Y_2 , it stabilizes at lower values. The mean value of Y_g (solid blue line) remains relatively consistent across most of the band groups, except for noticeable increases in Y_{15} and Y_{16} that start at 150 kHz and 160 kHz. The minimum value of Y_g (yellow dashed line) remains very low and relatively stable across most of the band groups. Moreover, Y_{15} shows a significant peak in mean voltage and maximum voltage, indicating unusual behavior in this band group. However, Y_1 that start from 50 Hz up to 10 kHz (excluding the fundamental tone) has a value higher compared to others.

About the current from coil 1, the maximum value of Y_g (red dashed line) starts high in Y_1 and gradually decreases across the groups, stabilizing at lower levels beyond Y_3 . The mean value of Y_g (blue line) shows a similar decreasing trend but at a lower magnitude than the maximum values. The minimum value of Y_g (yellow dashed line) consistently stays at very low levels (approaching 0.001 RMS). The Y_{17} shows a sharp spike in maximum value, breaking the otherwise stable trend beyond Y_3 . Finally, about the current from coil 2, the maximum value of Y_g (red dashed line) starts extremely high at Y_1 and drops rapidly through Y_3 . It stabilizes at a much lower range but shows slight fluctuations. The mean value of Y_g (blue line) follows a similar declining trend and remains stable after Y_3 . The minimum value of Y_g (yellow dashed line) shows very low values, with minor fluctuations.

(a)

(b)

(c)

FIGURE 23: MEAN, MAX AND MIN VALUES OVER BAND GROUP FOR VOLTAGE (A) CURRENT ROGOWSKI COIL 1 (B) AND CURRENT ROGOWSKI COIL 2 (C)

Finally, for the measurement campaign performed in 2024, the following table resumes the maximum amplitudes of the band groups analysed overall measurement time. These values can be assumed as starting point for selecting the grid disturbances up to 150 kHz.

TABLE 2: MAXIMUM VALUE OF Y_g OVER BAND GROUPS OF MEASURED QUANTITIES

	Y_g								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
V	48.99	32.41	19.62	22.72	19.77	18.14	17.46	18.55	16.02
I_1	1.83	1.70	0.07	0.10	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01
I_2	159.64	1.21	0.13	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.02

	Y_g								
	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
V	17.53	18.13	16.39	14.47	20.51	29.07	24.57	17.27	4.49
I_1	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.01
I_2	0.10	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.61	0.04

4.1 Software for numeric generation of complex waveforms

The development of an advanced waveform generation library in LabVIEW addresses the need for enhanced capabilities in generating power quality (PQ) waveforms. This software serves the requirements of the ADMIT project by allowing the creation of highly detailed waveforms, including harmonic disturbances up to 150 kHz. The library is built upon previous work from project 19NRM05 IT4PQ, upgrading the existing tool to support both AC and DC waveforms with significantly higher frequency components, offering flexibility for standard tests and custom experimental setups.

The software development process was structured into the following phases:

1. The existing software was reviewed to identify limitations in frequency range and waveform types. Specifications for extending the capabilities to include DC waveforms and disturbances up to 150 kHz were defined, ensuring alignment with ADMIT project goals.
2. The waveform generation algorithms were updated to handle higher frequency components. Key improvements included refining the data structures and processing pipelines to ensure stability and accuracy across the expanded range.
3. A VI, **Harmonic Disturbances**, was implemented to provide users with a flexible interface for generating waveforms with customizable fundamental frequencies and harmonic components. This functionality allows precise control over waveform parameters for both AC and DC scenarios.
4. The **Acquired Waveform Generation VI** was developed to allow seamless reproduction of waveforms recorded in previous measurement campaigns. This VI includes functionalities for data import, processing, and playback, ensuring compatibility with measurement data and providing a reliable platform for reproducibility.
5. The software was rigorously tested using simulated and real-world measurement data. Validation activities focused on verifying the accuracy of waveform generation, the ability to handle high-frequency disturbances, and the usability of the interface. Tests confirmed the software's capability to generate waveforms up to 150 kHz with high fidelity.

The waveform generation library, developed using National Instruments (NI) LabVIEW, consists of multiple modular components, each dedicated to implementing a specific power quality (PQ) phenomenon. These components, as illustrated in Fig. 4.1, are designed to operate independently, enabling high debugging efficiency and effective cross-checking. The modular architecture ensures flexibility and scalability in addressing various PQ phenomena. Users can configure parameters for each PQ phenomenon, allowing the creation of generic or customized waveforms. The library supports both stationary parameters (such as amplitude, phase, and frequency of the fundamental component) and disturbances, including harmonic distortion, interharmonic distortion, and short-duration variations (such as dips, swells, and interruptions) or transient phenomena. The software provides the ability to generate sinusoidal or distorted waveforms over multiple integer time intervals of the Fourier period or over arbitrary time intervals as specified by the user. The library automatically adjusts the duration of disturbances to ensure an integer multiple of the Fourier period, maintaining consistency and precision in waveform generation. The Fourier period is dynamically adapted based on the type of distortion and the selected generation frequency, ensuring that each inserted disturbance is an integer multiple of the waveform period. The calculation of the Fourier period is an integral function of the library. This function can be accessed programmatically, enabling user applications to coerce the waveform duration as needed. The function takes as input parameters the frequencies of all included disturbances and the generation frequency. It then calculates the Fourier period using the greatest common divisor, determined through Euclid's algorithm. This approach ensures the generated waveform is precise and optimized, with duration limits dependent only on the memory capacity of the hardware. This enhanced functionality within the ADMIT extension allows users to generate complex waveforms with high precision, supporting applications that require detailed PQ analysis and testing. The ADMIT Extension was developed by adding the generation of waveforms with high frequency components as independent module. For generation custom waveforms with high frequency components, the stationary disturbances, harmonic or interharmonic, can be used, as shown in Figure 24.

FIGURE 24: LIBRARY ARCHITECTURE WITH ADMIT EXTENSION

5 Identification of future measurement needs in the frequency range up to 150 kHz

In EMC and PQ standards, compatibility levels are defined as a reference level for the coordination of emission limits and immunity test levels for a given environment. They are also an indication of the expected level of disturbance in that environment. There is a set of “environment” EMC standards covering public networks at LV (EN 61000-2-2 [100]) and MV (EN 61000-2-12 [101]), as well as industrial networks (EN 61000-2-4 [102]). In reality, for the SH frequency interval, EN 61000-2-12 does not contain any indication limiting the scope to harmonic distortion. From the list of sources (arc furnaces, adjustable speed drives), it is also evident that twenty years ago, the impact on the grid of electric vehicles and renewables was not foreseen. The EN 61000-2-4 reports three environments, ‘1’ (or ‘2a’), ‘2b’, and ‘3’, the former corresponding to the residential/commercial LV environment of the EN 61000-2-2.

These levels were extensively discussed and compared in [103] for distortion caused by EVs during charging operations, considering harmonic and supraharmonic intervals. It is observed that two issues make the definitions of SH limits or compatibility levels more complex: first, the effect of the grid impedance and of resonances with variable factors of merit amplifying or attenuating emissions in terms of voltage and/or current [104]; second, when comparing values in the harmonic and supraharmonic ranges, the different resolution bandwidth and the narrowband or quasi-broadband behavior of components at different frequencies must be considered.

When EMC standards in a wide sense (including power quality standards, such as IEC 61000-4-7 [105] and IEC 61000-4-30 [106]) provide an indication of limits for conducted phenomena, low- and high-frequency and narrow- and broadband aspects have a significant influence on measurement and assessment methods. The following list exemplifies the most relevant factors that make a comparison between different standards difficult:

- Resolution bandwidth (RBW) is a relevant parameter, both when using a direct frequency-domain approach (e.g., a scanning receiver), or an indirect one, processing time-domain recordings by Discrete Fourier Transform. RBW values are usually standardized at 5 Hz [105], 200 Hz [107], 2 kHz [106], and 9 kHz [107]. The chosen RBW value has various implications:
- On the aggregation of nearby spectral components, for which the individual compliant spectral components can be measured as higher-amplitude equivalents no longer conforming to the limits;

it is reasonable that RBW values should be selected in agreement with the bandwidth of the victim; that is, power losses may be evaluated with large RBW values, whereas interference with PLC channels should be assessed with an RBW comparable to the channel width;

- On the response to complex time-varying waveforms containing impulsive and oscillatory parts [108], [109], for which a large RBW is able to track very fast signals, but loses resolution of the spectral representation;
- On the accuracy of the amplitude estimate of components [109], at least simply for the contribution of the incoherent noise falling within the measuring bandwidth, apart from the composition of different adjacent spectral components with their phase and time relationship into an equivalent one.

Apart from the influence of RBW on amplitude accuracy (as briefly discussed above), the intensity estimate for frequency-domain measurements is provided by amplitude detectors after demodulation during the scanning. Such detectors may be an rms detector, a peak detector, or a quasi-peak detector, the latter causing some concern. Its use is supported by CISPR and generally by RF EMC standards as an emissions weighting for a hypothetical jamming of analog radio transmissions for broadcasting purposes (no longer so widely used in the modern world of digital communication); its output being dependent on the time distribution of the spectral characteristics of the incoming signal, it can hardly be compared to a simpler rms or peak detector, as commented in [110] for impulsive emissions originating from pantograph electric arcs. Nonetheless, its application is still mandatory and has recently attracted a lot of effort to devise an efficient time-domain implementation [111], [112].

In general, the representation of time variability of disturbance in the short and long term is challenging for a matter of balancing accuracy and time granularity with the compactness of the representation. Standards IEC 61000-4-7 and IEC 61000-4-30 propose the aggregation of spectral components over intervals in the order of hundreds of ms (200 ms) and some seconds (3 s); IEC 61000-2-4 [113] states clearly that disturbance is assumed stationary over the 200 ms time interval. Longer aggregation times, such as 10-minute intervals or daily values, are required for the assessment of grid power quality and quantification of compatibility levels [114], but are not at all able to adequately represent spot scenarios of interference with victim equipment. This has two reasons: interference may take place in short time intervals and originate often from modulation byproducts with dynamics in the order of ms. An example of the latter is Figure 5 of [115], showing the pulsating spectrum of an EV input current causing flicker. If SH components are instead evaluated for relevance to human exposure to the electromagnetic field, the required averaging intervals are long, to evaluate impact in terms of thermal effects, as discussed in [116].

Emissions in the SH frequency interval are well covered for what concerns intentional (or in-band) and non-intentional (or out-of-band) emissions of PLC devices (standard EN 50065-1 [117]).

After the overall discussion of emissions and relevant parameters for their quantification, an underlying inconsistency must be underlined. Compatibility levels, as provided by EN 61000-2-4 at its Tables 4 and 5 for 2 kHz to 9 kHz and 9 kHz to 150 kHz intervals, are clearly covering differential mode for the following reasons: they follow a quantification of THD, the former levels for the 2 kHz to 9 kHz interval are provided as a percentage of the fundamental, and explicit reference is made to IEC 61000-4-7. Instead, emission limits are always provided for common-mode disturbance only, in line with CISPR standards. Immunity test levels are commonly in common mode as well, but EN 61000-4-19 [118] addresses immunity to differential-mode disturbance. Equivalency between differential-mode and common-mode levels is not exact, but, based on observed grid impedance values at high frequency, we can say that in the higher portion of the 2 kHz to 150 kHz interval, differential-mode and common-mode impedance values are quite similar, although the latter slightly larger.

Here, the focus is on levels and limits of the differential mode, for which we can consider the EN 61000-2-4 compatibility levels, ranging between about 1 V for classes 1 and 2a to 10 V for class 3 in the 2 kHz to 50 kHz interval, and between about 0.1 V for classes 1 and 2a to 10 V for class 3 in the 50 kHz to 150 kHz interval. It can be stated that:

- Environmental EMC standards (with notation 61000-2-X) should be updated and compatibility levels harmonized without dramatic changes.

- Present compatibility levels are such not to significantly penalize manufacturers of power conversion systems, either standalone or embedded (for a wide range of applications, such as EV charging, lighting, consumer electronics, etc.);
- If such environmental standards are duly considered normative references to limit emissions, adverse phenomena are under control; it goes without saying that EMC certification of products should be taken seriously, as well as verification of compliance once placed on the market.

There are documented negative effects (or, in general, “interference”) for different types of phenomena that have different intensity levels and time dynamics. For example, losses and self-heating are slower and appear at higher intensity than EMI to equipment, and in particular, PLC devices.

In general, the influencing mechanisms are such that a reference level (or limit) that reduces with frequency may be expected; losses are proportional to the square root of frequency, induction is proportional to frequency, and capacitive current increases with frequency. For interference with PLC devices, as the transmission level is constant over the operating frequency, a constant reference level may be expected, although a slight reduction in the received signal may be considered for increasing frequency (as caused by line attenuation).

From the previous discussion, we may consider the following points:

- Documented interference with PLC devices, considering both cases of presence and absence of interference; to this aim, the results shown in Figure 2 are used; values for mains signaling at the MV level are not established, as pointed out in EN 61000-2-12 [101], still in the 2003 version;
- Losses and consequential heating taking the harmonic limits as reference for the residential and industrial applications, namely considering the current distortion limits of EN 61000-3-2 (2019) [119] and EN 61000-3-12 (2019) [120], respectively; with a general assumption regarding the expected grid impedance, such limits are transformed into voltage distortion levels and then compared to those of EN 61000-2-2 (2019) [100] and EN 61000-2-4 (2020) [102];
- Effects at MV level, considering the critical values impacting the reliability of cable joints;
- Interference with energy meters and residual current devices.

With respect to the problem of interference with PLC devices, emission levels are reported in Figure 4 with overlaps of some annotations and a proposal for an overall reference level to be considered as a limit with respect to interference with PLCs alone. The purpose is to provide good coverage of the SH interval in terms of demonstrated interference cases, as well as lower levels in the same scenarios at which no interference occurred. The objective is attained when the “no interference” levels are sufficiently separated from the corresponding interference cases and also well leveled with respect to the corresponding “no interference” or “interference” cases at other frequency values nearby (to postulate homogeneous behavior at similar, but not the same, frequency values).

Three groups of points are highlighted by a dashed black circle and labeled as “A”, “B”, and “C”. Such points show some contradictory behavior with respect to the expected arrangement with the interference case (the square symbol) above the no interference case (the circle symbol):

- Group A: The points have a spread of 8 dB only, but with the interfering value reported as the lowest one; these values come from different PV inverters connected at the same grid, where interference was reported for one of the PLC devices in the same grid. It is thus possible that the attenuation from the source to the victim PLC is variable and accounts for some dB of variation, as well as that these values are not really interfering or not interfering with the PLC operation, as they fall outside the 42 kHz to 89 kHz Prime PLC operating band.
- Group B: similarly, this is an isolated point reported as interfering, but part of a broader spectrum where the interfering components fell inside the Prime PLC band.

- Group C: these two pairs at 35 kHz and 40 kHz are also very likely outside the operating band of the PLC in question, whereas confirmed interference for the square symbols is caused by the other points of the same case (blue squares) at 60 kHz and 70 kHz.

FIGURE 25: DETAILS OF THE EMISSION LEVELS OF FIGURE 2 WITH SUPERPOSED PROPOSED LIMIT CURVE (DASHED GRAY). GROUPS “A”, “B”, AND “C” ARE DISCUSSED IN THE TEXT.

In Figure 25, a thick dashed gray line is proposed (as a limit of 100 dB μ V above about 20 kHz with two variants with different slopes): this limit curve separates the circles from the squares, i.e., the “no interference” cases from the “interference” cases. The proposed limit of emission of 0.1 V provides a margin of more than an order of magnitude with respect to the Level 3 immunity levels of EN 61000-4-19 [118].

It is observed that such division is approximate, especially at a low frequency where the points are at the margin or outside the typical PLC band (in principle extended from 3 to 95 kHz and identified as a CENELEC “A band” in [121]).

In addition, it is possible to observe that higher levels may be allowed at lower frequencies, just moving the corner point slightly back to about 20 kHz and tilting the dashed limit curve (resulting in the other darker dash-dot profile). It can be noted that in the low-frequency part of the SH interval, between approximately 2 and 15 kHz, the variability of the proposed profile is significant and reference values here should be justified with other considerations, based on different approaches, such as extension of the harmonic limits for generic interference with equipment and limitation of losses, as well as other mechanisms of aging and deterioration (for example, for MV cable joints), both considered in the following.

This section contains a working example of the assignment of convenient SH current limits, starting from two assumptions. First, the harmonic limits for residential (16 A) and industrial (75 A) loads aim at limiting power losses and self-heating; values are shown in Table 2, to divide then for the respective reference current values $I_{r,Res}$ and $I_{r,Ind}$ to obtain the limit in %. Secondly, the number of SH components is known and is assigned for three sub-bands of the SH interval, namely 2 kHz to 9 kHz (in this example, three components), 9 kHz to 50 kHz (in this example, three components) and 50 kHz to 150 kHz (in this example, six components). This assumption is in line with what is reported in [122] for a complex load such as the inductive charger of an electric bus.

A Total SupraHarmonic Distortion (TSHD) index is considered similar to the classic Total Harmonic Distortion (THD); that is, corresponding to the root of the sum of the square of normalized component amplitudes. The use of subscript “I” indicates that the index refers to the current.

Each component is combined with the others of the same sub-band with a square-root-of-frequency criterion, trying to balance the partial contribution to the heat of each sub-band, and then the complete

TSHDI is calculated. It is the same as the estimated THDI, following the limit of the respective standards for residential or industrial applications. The industrial case is taken with short circuit ratio $R_{sc} = 66$. The result is shown in Figure 5, having also estimated the allowed tolerable voltage distortion by taking the reference current $I_{r,Res}$ as 16 A and $I_{r,Ind}$ as 75 A, and having estimated the grid impedance using the curve of Figure 20 of the IEC 62578 standard [123]. The absolute impedance values are as follows: 3.7 Ω at 2 kHz, 5.22 Ω at 9 kHz, 14.41 Ω at 50 kHz, and 32.72 Ω at 150 kHz. The reference voltage values $V_{r,Res}$ and $V_{r,Ind}$ are taken as 230 V and 400 V, respectively.

The resulting SH limits in % are almost the same for the residential and industrial cases: this is due to the THDI limit value, used as a reference that is 15% and 16% in the two cases.

It is also remarked upon that for a larger number of components in each sub-band (NSH-B1, NSH-B2 and NSH-B3), the corresponding limit must be reduced. The reduction factor (k_{B1} , k_{B2} and k_{B3} , respectively,) would be proportional to the square root of this number compared to the studied case dependent is not necessary, as the investigated effect is the power loss and consequential heating that follows by its own nature an rms summation.

6 Performance requirements for Voltage and Current Transformers

IEC 61869-1 introduces an original and modernized way to present the accuracy requirements of instrument transformers (Table 3: Accuracy requirement for harmonics up to 150 kHz), particularly under non-sinusoidal conditions such as those caused by harmonics.

TABLE 3: ACCURACY REQUIREMENT FOR HARMONICS UP TO 150 KHZ

Accuracy class	Ratio error at frequencies shown below			Phase error at frequencies shown below		
	%			Degrees		
WB1	$f_r < f \leq 1$ kHz	$1 < f \leq 1,5$ kHz	$1,5 < f \leq 3$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 1$ kHz	$1 < f \leq 1,5$ kHz	$1,5 < f \leq 3$ kHz
WB2	$f_r < f \leq 5$ kHz	$5 < f \leq 10$ kHz	$10 < f \leq 20$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 5$ kHz	$5 < f \leq 10$ kHz	$10 < f \leq 20$ kHz
WB3	$f_r < f \leq 20$ kHz	$20 < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 20$ kHz	$20 < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz
WB4	$f_r < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz	$150 < f \leq 500$ kHz	$f_r < f \leq 50$ kHz	$50 < f \leq 150$ kHz	$150 < f \leq 500$ kHz
0,1	± 1	± 2	± 5	± 1	± 2	± 5
0,2 – 0,2 S	± 2	± 4	± 5	± 2	± 4	± 5
0,5 – 0,5 S	± 5	± 10	± 10	± 5	± 10	± 20
1	± 10	± 20	± 20	± 10	± 20	± 20
Protection	± 10	± 20	± 30	-	-	-

These harmonics vary depending on the network configuration and voltage level, and are particularly relevant for:

- Measurement systems
- Power quality analysis
- Protection functions

To address this, the standard allows the use of accuracy class extensions that describe an instrument transformer's performance at higher frequencies:

- WB0: up to the 13th harmonic
- WB1: up to 3 kHz
- WB2: up to 20 kHz
- WB3: up to 150 kHz

These extensions are appended to the base accuracy class (e.g., Class 0.5-WB1) and provide a simple but effective way to communicate performance across a range of harmonic frequencies. For LPITs and SAMUs at least the WB0 extension is mandatory. For conventional instrument transformers, all extensions are

optional. Multiple extensions may be declared where applicable (e.g., Class 0.2-WB1 and Class 0.5-WB2). The system applies equally to voltage and current transformers. This extension system is a key innovation in IEC 61869-1, reflecting the evolving needs of modern power systems that include harmonics and wideband signal content.

In the context of IT assessments, metrological traceability and the associated measurement uncertainty are critical to ensuring the validity of conformity assessments. The concept of metrological traceability refers to the property of a measurement result whereby it can be related to a reference, typically an SI unit, through an unbroken and documented chain of calibrations, each contributing to the overall measurement uncertainty. National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) provide calibration and traceability to the SI system of a transfer standard, such as a current or voltage comparator, reference transformer, or another high-accuracy device. This transfer standard is then used by laboratories or IT manufacturers to verify the accuracy of their instrument transformers.

NMIs are able to perform the calibration of transfer standards with the best achievable uncertainty, denoted U_{NMI} . This value represents the lowest possible uncertainty under controlled laboratory conditions and includes all relevant components such as the performance of the standard, reference values, environmental influences, and traceability to national or international standards. When this transfer standard is subsequently used by the manufacturer to assess an instrument transformer, the total measurement uncertainty increases due to several additional factors, including: Measurement setup effects (e.g., cabling, connections), operator variability, environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, electromagnetic interference), Influence of the transformer under test (e.g., loading effects, saturation, drift, linearity), resolution and linearity of the measuring instruments.

In practical applications, these additional influences are often estimated to increase the uncertainty by a factor, usually between 3 and 5, relative to U_{NMI} . This leads to a total expanded uncertainty for the calibration of the instrument transformer:

$$U_{IT} = (3 \text{ to } 5) \times U_{NMI} \quad (1)$$

According to best practices in metrology, the uncertainty of the calibration process should be significantly lower than the tolerance or accuracy of the device under test, typically by a factor of 3. This is commonly referred to as the Test Uncertainty Ratio (TUR), which is calculated as:

$$TUR = \frac{\text{Accuracy IT}}{U_{IT}} \geq 3 \quad (2)$$

For example, at 50 Hz or 60 Hz, NMIs can calibrate transfer standards with an uncertainty typically around 0.002%. According to equation (1), this results in a total uncertainty in the range of 0.006% to 0.01%. If an IT with a declared accuracy of 0.1% is being assessed, the resulting TUR ranges from 10 to 16, comfortably exceeding the minimum recommended value of 3 for reliable conformity assessment. Therefore, the achieved uncertainty level is fully compliant with metrological requirements for the assessment of an instrument transformer with a 0.1% accuracy class at 50 Hz. This confirms that the traceability chain, from the NMI to the transfer standard and from the transfer standard to the instrument transformer, is robust and suitable. The expanded uncertainty remains within acceptable limits, ensuring that decisions of conformity or non-conformity are statistically reliable and metrologically justified.

To determine the minimum accuracy requirement for ITs operating up to 150 kHz, equations (1) and (2) should be combined, resulting in (3):

$$\text{Accuracy IT} \geq (9 \text{ to } 15) \times U_{NMI} \quad (3)$$

Since degrades with increasing frequency due to the frequency response of the reference equipment and system limitations due the small level of harmonics which poses a challenge for accurate measurement. ITs used up to 150 kHz are typically designed with technologies where the fundamental output is scaled down to standard values such as 1 Vp to be compatible with conventional acquisition systems. However, harmonic components are usually less than 1 % of the fundamental, and therefore their output voltages are significantly lower, often in the millivolt range. This makes the reliable measurement of these components difficult, especially when considering the resolution, linearity, and noise floor of the measuring instruments. As a result, the ability to characterize harmonic performance is directly influenced by the limitations of the measurement system itself.

Two main methods can be used to assess the performance of ITs at higher frequencies:

- Frequency sweep method (simplified method): injecting a known sinusoidal signal at various frequencies into the IT and measuring the output voltage or current.
- Multitoned method (reference method): injecting a fundamental signal superimposed with one or several harmonic components and measuring the resulting output quantity.

Both methods lead to an increase in measurement uncertainty as the frequency rises. The uncertainty budget becomes the limiting factor when determining whether an IT meets a given accuracy class at a specific frequency. We can derive the minimum required accuracy of the instrument transformer as a function of the NMI's typical calibration uncertainty at each frequency range. This process is performed inversely: instead of computing the uncertainty from a given IT accuracy, we determine the minimum accuracy requirement that still satisfies the $TUR \geq 3$ criterion. The two tables below have been developed based on this approach and are differentiated by the relative amplitude of harmonic components:

- Table 4 assumes the harmonic component at the output of the IT under consideration has an amplitude of 10 mV and 1 mV, using the first method.
- Table 5 considers the harmonic component under consideration using the second method.

TABLE 4: RECOMMENDED MINIMUM ACCURACY FOR HARMONICS USING THE FIRST METHOD

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical U_{NMI}	Minimum required IT Accuracy
>10 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.01%	0.15%
	10 kHz – 150 kHz	0.02%	0.30%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.03%	0.45%
>1 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.06%	0.9%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2%	3,0%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.3%	4.5%
>10 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.02%	0.15%
	10 kHz – 150 kHz	0.03%	0.30%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.05%	0.45%
>1 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.1%	0.9%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2%	3,0%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.3%	4.5%

TABLE 5: RECOMMENDED MINIMUM ACCURACY FOR HARMONICS USING THE SECOND METHOD

Amplitude of harmonics at the output of IT	Frequency Range	Typical U_{NMI}	Minimum required IT Accuracy
>10 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.05%	0.75%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.1%	1.5%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.1%	1.5%
>1 mV	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.5%	7.5%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	1%	15%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	1.5%	22%
>10 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.1%	0.75%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	0.2%	1.5%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	0.2%	1.5%
>1 mA	1 kHz to 10 kHz	0.5%	7.5%
	10 kHz – 100 kHz	1%	15%
	100 kHz – 150 kHz	1.5%	22%

The tables show that the alignment between theoretical metrological constraints and IEC61869-2024 requirement are consistent when the output voltage of the IT is higher than 10 mV using both methods. When the voltage is lower, the minimum required specification surpasses sometimes what is mentioned in

the IEC61869-2024. So, it is then important to determine conditions of the minimum output voltage of harmonics, which is proportional to the percentage of harmonics relative to the fundamental.

Indeed, when measuring high voltage signals that include superimposed harmonic components, the measurement uncertainty can vary significantly depending on several key factors:

- Scale Factor of the IT, typically used to scale down high voltage signals to standard levels, such as 1 V or 10 V, suitable for acquisition systems (usually with 16-bit or 18-bit resolution). The chosen scale factor directly affects the magnitude of the output signal. If the scale factor results in a low output voltage, especially for harmonic components, the relative uncertainty increases due to limitations in resolution and noise floor of the measuring system.
- Percentage of Harmonics: Harmonic components are often much smaller in amplitude than the fundamental frequency. When these small signals are measured at low voltage levels (e.g., due to high scaling or weak harmonic presence), they approach the resolution limit of the data acquisition system. As a result, the signal-to-noise ratio deteriorates, leading to degraded measurement accuracy and increased uncertainty for harmonic content.
- Resolution and Noise of the Measuring System: The effective resolution of the acquisition system limits the ability to detect small voltage changes. For low-amplitude harmonics superimposed on a high voltage signal, the quantization error, inherent noise, and possible aliasing effects become more significant, further contributing to the overall uncertainty.

The first method (simplified one) gives better accuracy assessment compared with the first second one (reference one) but do not give any possible interactions between the fundamental component and the harmonics component.

However, some rated conditions need to be specified to better meet these accuracy requirements.

7 Selection of the types of ITs

TABLE 6: SELECTION OF ITs INVOLVED

#	Partner	VT / CT	Technology	Rated Input	Rated Output	Frequency
1	UNIBO	VT	Resistive	$20/\sqrt{3}$ kV	$3.25/\sqrt{3}$ kV	50/60 Hz
2	LNE	VT	Resistive	75 kV	75 V	50/60 Hz
3	LNE	VT	RC	50 kV	100 V	50/60 Hz
4	SUN	VT	Inductive	3 kV	100 V	50/60 Hz

8 Definition of voltage and current levels

This section establishes appropriate voltage and current levels – informed by standards, literature, and recent research – for testing medium-voltage (MV) instrument transformers (measurement transformers) under high-frequency distortion conditions (supraharmonics up to 150 kHz). This includes summarizing key findings from previous activities, identifying recommended practices/guidelines, comparing results across sources, and noting any gaps or needed additional information.

Instrument transformers (voltage transformers VTs and current transformers CTs) are useful to scale down power system voltages and currents for metering and protection. Traditional accuracy specifications and test methods cover only power frequency (50 / 60 Hz) and low harmonics. However, supraharmonic distortion – defined as high-frequency components in the range 2 kHz to 150 kHz – is increasingly present in modern grids due to the proliferation of power electronic devices (inverters for solar/wind plants, EV chargers, LED drives, etc.). Supraharmonics can impact power quality (PQ), causing additional losses, insulation stress, and potential malfunctions in equipment and measurement devices.

The recently released IEC 61869-1 Edition 2 Standard, issued in 2023, extends instrument transformer accuracy classes over five wideband ranges up to 500 kHz. In effect, manufacturers can specify accuracy of voltage and current transformers, voltage dividers and current sensors for HF components (denoted classes WB0–WB4) – but the Standard doesn't provide very clear procedures or required waveforms to check the accuracy of conventional and low-power instrument transformers at those frequencies. As a result, there is a gap in how to characterize and verify instrument transformer performance at high frequency. To ensure reliable PQ measurements in the 9–150 kHz band range, realistic test waveforms and harmonics levels must be defined.

There is currently no direct standard which provides specific voltage/current test levels for instrument transformers at supraharmmonic frequencies. Relevant standards provide context but not limits:

- IEC 61000-4-7 / -4-30 (EMC and PQ measurement standards) classify disturbances up to 150 kHz and recommend measurement methods (e.g. 2 kHz bands). They recognize “induced continuous waves” and “oscillatory transients” in this range, but do not specify compatibility levels for MV networks or test amplitudes for transformers. In practice, compatibility levels (commonly a few % of nominal) are often cited for lower frequencies (<2 kHz); above 9 kHz, no uniform emission limits exist yet in MV grid standards.
- IEEE 1159 (Power Quality monitoring) similarly classifies high-frequency phenomena but gives no numeric limits for 2–150 kHz in MV systems.
- IEC 61869-1 Ed.2 (2023) does define a method for determining the accuracy of ITs and LPITs for harmonics, based on the assigned wideband (WB) class. Still, the methodology as established in the standard is not fully detailed and presents significant limitations depending on the particular characteristics of the sensor to be characterized or the harmonic level to be verified. Notably, the IEC standard does not define the value of the harmonic percentage with respect to the fundamental signal that should be applied. This new version of the standard extends instrument transformer accuracy classes to cover high frequencies. Five wideband classes WB0–WB4 are defined, e.g. WB4 spans up to 500 kHz. However, the standard does not indicate how to test for these classes – it neither prescribes test waveforms nor states what magnitude of HF voltage/current to apply. It simply defines accuracy as a percentage error allowable in those frequency bands, leaving implementation to laboratories. For traditional inductive transformers (VTs/CTs), all wideband classes are optional; only low-power instrument transformers (LPITs), voltage divider and current sensors, the WB0 class requirements shall be at least satisfied.
- IEC Technical Committees: Several IEC TCs are examining supraharmonics (TC77A for EMC, TC38 for instrument transformers, TC8 for grid integration, etc.). Some have issued Technical Reports – e.g. IEC TR 63222-3 lists common sources of supraharmonics (EV chargers, PV inverters, etc.) and affected equipment – but binding test requirements are still under development. In this context, the IEC TC 38 "Instrument transformers" has assigned the task to TC38/WG47 "Evolution of Instrument transformer requirements for the modern market" to establish Task Forces to study the topic of extended frequency response qualification of Instrument Transformers for PQ measurement and travelling waves relaying applications and to study the topic relevant to the effects of combined influencing factors on the accuracy of Instrument Transformers. In addition, TC38 has identified a series of needs and open issues concerning the definition of measurement methods and test procedures for assessing the accuracy performance of ITs intended to be used for Power Quality Measurements, which have been submitted to the STAIR/EMPIR Committee.
- Given the standards' gap, literature reviews and measurement campaigns to analyze the levels and effects of supraharmonics in the grid have been performed in previous activities and described in previous sections.

8.1 Literature review

Both literature and standards are summarized to define “significant waveforms to test ITs”. It concludes with some key consolidated points:

- **Amplitude-Frequency Ranges:** It confirms that supraharmmonic sources (PV, wind, EV) typically inject frequencies below 50 kHz with amplitudes generally below 0.3 V; in some high-PV scenarios, up to 0.15 V at 126 kHz was found, likely due to resonances. Dominant emissions: 10 kHz (wind), 12–16 kHz (PV and EV chargers), sometimes with smaller multiples (32, 48, 68 kHz, etc.). In EV charging tests, 10 kHz components up to 1080 mA (at 16 A charge) and 45 kHz components ~200 mA (at 23 A charge) were recorded, meaning 4–5% of the 23 A current in a troublesome case. Those are among the higher reported percentages on the current side. Still, they were local to the device; once propagating through a transformer, the grid-side effect is smaller.
- **Propagation Attenuation:** The review details how supraharmonics propagate across transformers with various transfer ratios. A crucial observation: MV to LV transfer can sometimes amplify certain frequencies. For example, one measurement showed a 0.5 V LV distortion became ~1.5 V on the MV side at a resonance (transfer ratio 3 V/V). Generally, though, MV/LV transformers attenuate HF: often a 1 V LV distortion yields only 0.01–0.5 V on MV (i.e. <50% of turns ratio). This implies an instrument transformer on the MV side could see at most a few tenths of a percent of nominal from any single supraharmmonic that originated in LV.
- **Conclusions for Testing:** To quote the paper, “The analysis of on-site results has shown it is difficult to define typical values... however, in general the frequencies are tied to converter switching and amplitudes do not exceed 5% in 9–150 kHz”. Moreover, “test procedures must replicate actual operational conditions, i.e., fundamental plus disturbances”. The document recommends testing wideband accuracy by applying a fundamental and superimposing multiple high frequency components up to 5%, then evaluating the transformer’s output using the same PQ indices that a meter would use (e.g., measure how much the HF is attenuated or phase-shifted by the transformer).

As a summary, the document recommends testing the accuracy of the ITs at the following current and voltage levels:

- **Voltage test levels:** ~0.5% to 5% of nominal RMS per HF component, depending on frequency. In MV terms, this is on the order of 0.1% (for higher kHz) up to 1% (for low kHz where emissions cluster). For example, appropriate bands would be in the order of 5% of nominal for 2–10 kHz band, 2% for 10–50 kHz and 1% for 50–150 kHz. This aligns with literature: lower-frequency “supraharmonics” overlap with high-order harmonics, which occasionally reach a few percent (e.g., some PV inverters had ~2% at 2.5 kHz, whereas above 50 kHz it’s typically < 1%).
- **Current test levels:** A similar percentage rated current. If a CT is rated 200/1 A, injecting up to ~1 A of HF (0.5%) would be appropriate. In many cases, supraharmmonic currents are limited by device filters and don’t approach 1% at MV level. But testing up to 1% ensures covering a broad range of scenarios, including an aggregation of many devices.

8.2 Measurement campaign

A field measurement campaign was conducted in 2024 on a medium-voltage network in Milan (Unareti 23 kV feeder supplying EV charging stations). This study directly measured the natural supraharmmonic content on an MV system over several months. Key findings include:

- **Supraharmmonic Voltage Levels:** The measured MV phase-to-ground voltage distortion in 9-150 kHz was in the order of a few tens of volts (RMS) per 10 kHz band. Table 2 compiles the maximum RMS voltage in each 10 kHz band group (Y1: 50 Hz–10 kHz through Y18: 170–180 kHz). The highest HF voltage observed was about 29.07 V in the 140–150 kHz band, and values in most bands were 15–25 V or lower. Even the 9–10 kHz band (Y2) peaked at ~32.4 V. Considering the MV rated voltage of 20 kV, these correspond to extremely small fractions (~0.1–0.2%). For perspective, 29 V of HF

on 20 kV is 0.15 % of nominal. The 50 Hz–10 kHz band (excluding the fundamental) had a higher residual (~49 V), but that primarily reflects low-order harmonics up to 9 kHz.

- **Supraharmonic Current Levels:** The currents were measured via Rogowski coils on the LV side of the substation transformers (since the MV feeder load flows into two 0.4 kV, 400–630 kVA transformers). Maximum HF current components varied widely between the two measured paths (likely due to different loading). Current I1 had a highest HF component ~1.83 A in the 0–10 kHz band, dropping to < 0.1 A beyond 20 kHz. Current I2 showed an anomalous 159 A reading in the 0–10 kHz band (this may include a fundamental leakage or an outlier), but beyond that it too dropped to ~1.2 A at 10–20 kHz and ≤ 0.1 A above 20 kHz [3]. Thus, typical HF currents in the LV circuit were well below 1 A RMS for $f > 20$ kHz. On the MV 15 A line side, that would translate to only a few milliamps of HF current after accounting for the transformer ratio.

This measurement campaign supports setting supraharmonic test voltages in the tens-of-volts range for MV transformers. For a 20 kV class VT, it would be appropriate to apply e.g. 50 V at 10 kHz, 30 V at ~150 kHz, etc., simultaneously with the rated 20 kV/ $\sqrt{3}$ fundamental. Likewise, for a CT rated e.g. 100 A, it would be appropriate to superimpose supraharmonics in the order of 0.5 - 1 A in the lower kHz (1% HF distortion) and a few hundred mA at higher kHz to emulate worst-case conditions.

In summary, previous activities conclude that testing with supraharmonic voltage/current components on the order of 1-5 % of the transformer's rating. This aligns with both typical supraharmonic magnitudes recorded on-site and protective considerations. The exact values within that range can be adjusted by frequency band. For example, 5 % of the nominal rating in the lower supraharmonic range, while 1–3 % in the upper supraharmonic range. In any case, to harmonize the voltage and current injection through all frequencies, it might be appropriate to aim to the same percentage of supraharmonics through the whole frequency range from 9 – 150 kHz. An example of the voltage and current levels based on this percentage is given below:

- Regarding the voltage levels, for example, testing a 20 kV VT with a 5 % of high-frequency content distributed across relevant frequencies would mean injecting up to 1000 V of supraharmonics from 9-150 kHz.
- Regarding the current levels, for example, testing a 200 A CT with a 5 % of high-frequency content distributed across relevant frequencies would mean injecting 10 A of supraharmonics from 9-150 kHz.

Additionally, two further considerations can be added to the conclusions, as it would be appropriate to assess them during the next activities that will be carried out in WP2 and WP3:

- The influence of the injected voltage/current value on the LPIT: If the applied levels at the input are too low, the resulting signals at the output may be of very low magnitude. This can lead to technical limitations when trying to obtain results with low measurement uncertainty.
- The influence of the employed methodology: It is possible that determining a sensor's accuracy for a specific harmonic level alone is not equivalent to evaluating the sensor's response when this harmonic is superimposed on the fundamental frequency. Although this methodology is accepted by IEC 61869-1, there is no evidence that the results obtained are equivalent in all cases.

9 Definition of rated test conditions

9.1 Simplified method

The simplified procedure is designed to assess the instrument transformer, when subjected to both a high-voltage fundamental signal and low-voltage harmonic components. The test could be carried out in two main steps. In Step 1, the accuracy at fundamental is assessed according to the relative IEC standard. As expressed above the accuracy requirement is in accordance with the traceability chain at 50 Hz. In Step 2,

a frequency sweep ranging from 9 kHz to 150 kHz is injected to evaluate the IT response to harmonics. The measurement system compares the output of the IT with the input.

FIGURE 26: SIMPLIFIED PROCEDURE FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF IT

The test rated conditions are:

- The IT is positioned in a controlled environment with a defined free air zone, typically with a minimum spacing of twice the height ($2 \times H$) in all directions. This free space is critical to avoid proximity effects, such as capacitive coupling or electromagnetic interference from surrounding objects, which could distort the measured signals—especially at high frequencies or for low-level harmonics. Maintaining this free air volume minimizes unwanted interactions and ensures that the measured response accurately reflects the performance of the IT itself, not the influence of nearby structures or cables. The assigned cable is also used under controlled conditions to carry the signal and preserve the integrity of the measurement.
- The setup must ensure that signal levels remain at the output above 10 mV at the comparator inputs, which is critical to maintain a minimal accuracy requirement as described before especially for the assessment of IT with 0.1 % class.
- The IT is assessed using his assigned cable and burden to ensure that it does not introduce additional distortion or uncertainty into the measurement chain.
- The traceability chain need to be unbroken of the measuring systems need to be unbroken.

9.2 Reference method

This reference procedure is designed to assess the frequency response—both in amplitude and phase—of a high-voltage measurement system, such as a voltage divider or instrument transformer (IT), when subjected to realistic signal conditions. The generator delivers a signal composed of a high-voltage fundamental component combined with either a single harmonic tone or a multi-tone waveform, simulating actual distorted signals encountered in power systems. The DUT is exposed to this composite waveform, and its output is compared against a reference using a high-accuracy comparator. This approach, using combined fundamental and harmonic signals, is particularly valuable for evaluating how the measurement system behaves under real-world power quality conditions, where non-sinusoidal waveforms are common. It ensures that the IT maintains accuracy not only at the nominal frequency but also across the relevant harmonic or broadband spectrum.

FIGURE 27: REFERENCE MEASURING SYSTEM

The test rated conditions are:

- Positioning as method 1.
- Comparator (>1 MHz of bandwidth, >16 bits, harmonics higher of at least 1 % > 1 MS/s)
- The IT is assessed using his assigned cable and burden to ensure that it does not introduce additional distortion or uncertainty into the measurement chain.
- The traceability chain needs to be unbroken.

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